

Task 47, TURBINIA, Turbulent Inflow Innovative Aerodynamics
Final Technical Report Phase I

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Abstract

The report presents the final outcomes of IEA TCP Wind Task 47, TURBulent INflow Innovative Aerodynamics, TURBINIA, Phase I, conducted from January 2021 to December 2024. The project was executed by a consortium of 29 entities from academia and industry across 8 countries.

- Denmark: Technical University of Denmark, DTU, Siemens-Gamesa Renewable Energy
- France: IFPEN, LHEEA lab - Centrale Nantes/CNRS , ONERA,
- Germany: ForWind/Fraunhofer IWES, Kiel University of Applied Sciences, University of Stuttgart, WindNovation, Enercon, Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. DLR, University of Applied Sciences Emden
- Italy: CNR-INM, PoliMi, University of Rome "La Sapienza", University of Rome "Roma Tre", University of Florence, Politecnico di Bari (PoliBa)
- Netherlands: TNO Energy Transition (Operating Agent), Delft University of Technology, TUDelft, DNV, Suzlon Blade Technology, SBT, CWI, LM and University of Twente, UTwente
- Sweden: Uppsala University, Campus Gotland,
- Switzerland: Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences (OST)
- USA: National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), Sandia National Laboratory (SNL), University of Massachusetts (UMass)

The project focussed on measurements and modelling of detailed aerodynamic properties along the blade of large-scale turbines. Collaboration in detailed aerodynamic measurements proved highly beneficial, as the specialized nature of these measurements made sharing best practices particularly valuable. However, data restrictions limited the ability to conduct joint validations based on these measurements. An exception was the DanAero experiment on a 2MW turbine, for which the machine data are available so that they could be simulated with a wide variety of aerodynamic models, ranging from low-fidelity Blade Element Momentum (BEM) methods to high-fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) models, with mid-fidelity models in between. In addition several comparison rounds were conducted based on a mutual comparison of calculational results from low fidelity models versus results from higher fidelity models. This included simulations on the 15 MW IEA Reference Wind Turbine (RWT). The comparisons revealed discrepancies in fatigue load predictions, with BEM-based models tending to overpredict fatigue loads, underscoring the need for improved modeling. It was also found that torsion angles on the 15 MW RWT are significant even at moderate wind speeds. This observation, together with the fact that substantial differences are found in partners' results of these angles, where torsion angles strongly influence the aerodynamic loads, emphasizes the importance of improving torsion angle predictions. Differences in inflow modelling also yielded notable variations in load predictions that need to be addressed. Resolving this, amongst others, necessitates aerodynamic measurements along the rotor blade coupled with a detailed mapping of the flow field.

Chapter 1

Introduction: Background and goal

1.1 Introduction and background

This report describes the results of IEA Task 47 TURBulent INflow Innovative Aerodynamics, TURBINIA which is carried out as an IEA Wind Task, i.e. a collaborative international project organised under the auspices of the Technology Collaboration Program (TCP) Wind from the International Energy Agency (IEA).

In TURBINIA the following countries and parties participated (between brackets the contact persons are listed):

- Denmark: Technical University of Denmark, DTU (H. Madsen, G. Pirrung, C. Grinderslev, N. Sørensen), Siemens-Gamesa Renewable Energy (A. Gomez Gonzalez)
- France: IFPEN (W. Gonçalves Pinto, F. Blondel, N. Bonfils), LHEEA lab - Centrale Nantes/CNRS (C. Braud), ONERA (R. Boisard)
- Germany: ForWind/Fraunhofer IWES (B. Stoevesandt, L. Honig), Kiel University of Applied Sciences (A.P. Schaffarczyk, B.A. Lobo, S. Risius, Wang ZhongXia), University of Stuttgart (T. Lutz), WindNovation (K. Hummel), Enercon (T. Kuehn), Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. DLR (M. Imiela, O. Hach, P. Seelemeyer, J. Klassen), University of Applied Sciences Emden (I. Herraez)
- Italy: Politecnico di Milano, PoliMi (A. Croce, S. Cacciola), CNR - INM (L. Greco, C. Testa, N. Aryan, C. Brancaccio), University of Rome "La Sapienza" (A. Castorrini), University of Rome "Roma Tre" (R. Camussi), University of Florence (A. Bianchini, F. Papi, L. Pagamonci), Politecnico di Bari (S. Cherubini, P. De Palma, C. Bernardi, A. Giannotta)
- Netherlands: Netherlands Organisation for Applied Research, TNO (G. Schepers, K. Boorsma), Delft University of Technology, TUDelft (N. Aryan, Wei Yu), DNV (G. Bangga, M. Kloosterman), Suzlon Blade Technology, SBT (C. Rodriguez), Research Institute for Mathematics and Computer science in the Netherlands, CWI (B. Sanderse), LM WindPower (A. Herring, M. Kloosterman) and University of Twente, UTwente (H. Ozdemir)
- Sweden: Uppsala University, Campus Gotland, (S. Ivanell)
- Switzerland: Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences (J. Deparday, S. Barber)
- USA: National Renewable Energy Laboratory, NREL (J. Jonkman), Sandia National Laboratory SNL (C. Kelley), University of Massachusetts, UMass (E. Branlard)

The focus of TURBINIA was on validating and improving aerodynamic (and related aero-elastic) models for large 10MW+ turbines. The project builds upon previous IEA Tasks, specifically IEA Task 14, 18, 20, and 29. For more details about these former IEA Tasks, refer to [1–7]. Essentially, all previous Tasks

addressed challenges for various types of aerodynamic models, but for smaller turbines than those considered in the present Task.

Such aerodynamic models play a crucial role in industrial wind turbine design codes. They are key to predicting power production, loads, and aero-elastic stability. Various models are employed, ranging from low-fidelity to high-fidelity, each with its own strengths and limitations. The trade-off between model fidelity and computational efficiency is the most critical consideration. In this context, computational time is significantly more crucial for wind energy calculations than for most other technological fields. This is especially true when determining the design load spectrum, which requires calculating and combining numerous 10-minute time series to capture wind statistics over the turbine’s entire lifetime. This process can involve tens of millions of time steps. Given that even a single time step demands a computationally intensive aerodynamic calculation—including the flow field from upstream to downstream, coupled with the full 3D aeroelastic behavior of the turbine—efficient computation becomes a major constraint. To address this, the industry relies on engineering models based on Blade Element Momentum (BEM) theory. However, while BEM-based models offer computational efficiency, they incorporate many simplifications and assumptions. Although these simplifications and assumptions are covered with so-called engineering add-ons to the BEM theory they are still low-fidelity. Despite the low fidelity level of these models, several validation exercises amongst others from the previous IEA Tasks on aerodynamics, resulted in successful code validation for uniform, constant inflow conditions and straight blades, provided that the input is carefully selected, mitigating the ‘human factor’ [8].

However, as stated before these previous validations were done on relatively small turbines. A key motivation for the present IEA Task is that the assumptions in BEM based engineering models become increasingly inadequate as turbine sizes grow, resulting in more pronounced limitations. One such assumption is uniform inflow. While this assumption holds reasonably well for small rotor planes with minimal flow incoherence, larger rotor planes experience much stronger shear, veer, and incoherent turbulence, deviating significantly from BEM theory’s assumptions. For example, figure 1.1 illustrates the extreme veer (i.e. variation in wind direction with height) over the year 2015 at the Met Mast IJmuiden site in the Dutch sector of the North Sea. The dashed lines indicate the boundaries of a 10 MW rotor plane. While veer remains limited in the lower atmosphere, where smaller turbines operate, it reaches approximately 40 degrees across the rotor plane of a 10 MW turbine. Such a large veer severely violates the uniform flow assumption (which corresponds to non-yawed conditions) in BEM theory. Although engineering add-ons for modelling yaw in BEM exist, they assume a constant yaw misalignment and fail to account for such extreme variations in yaw angle across the rotor plane.

An added challenge in modelling large rotors using BEM arises from the huge rotor size in itself which goes together with large blade deflections and vibrations leading to a much more complex flow-structure interaction.

All these factors result in a stronger violation of the assumptions in BEM-based engineering models as turbines increase in size despite the fact that these models remain indispensable due to their efficiency.

At the other end of the spectrum, high-fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) models offer greater accuracy at the cost of significantly increased computational effort. It is noted that CFD models can be further categorized by fidelity levels, with Large Eddy Simulations (LES) being higher fidelity than Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS)). Mid-fidelity approaches, such as free vortex wake (FVW) methods and panel methods, strike a balance by providing higher fidelity than engineering models but lower than CFD. They are more computationally efficient than CFD, yet less efficient than engineering models.

In TURBINIA, models of all fidelity levels are included, with a key strategy being the calibration of low-fidelity models with results from higher-fidelity models for large turbines. This was amongst others done on the 15 MW Reference Wind Turbine (RWT) as designed in IEA Task 37. From these simulations aerodynamic knowledge gap for the design of 15 MW scale turbines are identified.

Besides this modeling focus, there is an equally important emphasis on experiments. It should then be realized that conventional wind turbine measurements of e.g. power and blade root bending moment lack sufficient detail for the validation of rotor aerodynamic models, see [10] by which very special rotor aerodynamic experiments are needed (often denoted as detailed aerodynamic experiments). In these detailed aerodynamic experiments pressure distributions at different locations along the rotor blades should be measured anyhow where measurements of e.g. inflow velocities and boundary layer transition or even the drag are very nice to know. Such measurements are of a very special character and they have rarely

Figure 1.1: Shear (left) and extreme veer (wind direction as function of height, right) from the year 2015 at location of Met Mast IJmuiden in the North Sea (dashed lines indicate lower and upper part of rotor plane and hub height of 10 MW turbine), from [9]

been done, particularly not on MW scale, until recently several countries initiated large scale detailed aerodynamic measurement programs. They all went through a similar learning process on these measurement techniques, by which the time was found ripe to cooperate on this specialized field since sharing experiences is a very fruitful way to steepen the learning curves.

This cooperation between experimentalists is an important goal of TURBINIA but it is also desired to use these measurements as a basis for validation of aerodynamic models. This however suffers from the fact that machine data of most experiments in TURBINIA are restricted so they cannot be used (yet) for a joint validation round. Fortunately this was not true for the data from the DanAero experiment. This DanAero experiment was carried out at atmospheric field conditions on a 2MW turbine in a Danish project by Danish Technical University DTU and 4 industrial partners (LM WindPower, Siemens WindPower, Vestas and Dong Energy) in 2 periods from 2007 until 2010 and from 2010 until 2013. The level of detail from the instrumentation lies far above the level at conventional wind turbine measurements. Amongst others surface pressures and inflow velocities were measured at four sections along a blade and a row of surface flush mounted microphones was installed at the outer part of the blade enabling the study of transition and the surface pressure spectrum which is the source of trailing edge noise. The unique data from the DanAero experiment, including a description of the turbine, were made available to the participants. Therefore, the DanAero experiment could be used as validation material for a comparison round with calculational results.

This report first describes the goal of TURBINIA in section 1.2. Dissemination of results has taken place in very different forms, as explained in section 1.3. Then the working procedure and the work plan of TURBINIA is described in chapter 2. The simulations on the DanAero turbine are described in chapter 3 and the simulations on the 15 MW RWT in chapter 4. The aerodynamic experiments are described in chapter 5. In order to gain maximum benefit of the enhanced knowledge from TURBINIA for wind turbine design it should be integrated with the knowledge on other relevant disciplines. For this reason a number of cooperations with other IEA Tasks which have connections to aerodynamics are established. These are described in chapter 6. Finally the conclusions are given in chapter 7.

1.2 Goal

The aim of TURBINIA is to establish a collaboration among experts in specialized innovative aerodynamic field measurements, thereby accelerating the learning curve for these complex measurements. Furthermore, the cross-fertilization of aerodynamic theory and experimental data enhances the quality of both where also

a comparative analysis of model results from various fidelity levels will be undertaken, ultimately leading to enhanced and validated aerodynamic and aero-elastic models for the design of large-scale wind turbine blades operating in atmospheric inflow.

1.3 Dissemination

TURBINIA has resulted in numerous publications, presentations and contributions to dissemination events. There are many individual disseminations, see for example the many references on experiments, chapter 5, but also joint articles and presentations like [11–14]. Moreover there have been disseminations with other IEA Tasks, see chapter 6. Another dissemination with high impact is the Wind Energy Aerodynamics Handbook [15]. This handbook intends to become a main reference work for all questions on the field of wind turbine aerodynamics. Approximately 10 chapters of this Handbook are closely connected to TURBINIA.

Of special importance are strategic dissemination events. These are events for a non-aerodynamic audience with a more general focus. Several of these events have been held between TURBINIA participants and industry such as the SP4 workshop at EERA-JP Wind Innovation Event which was held in September 2023 and September 2024. Moreover DTU organised annual dissemination events entitled "Recent Achievements in Numerical and Experimental Rotor Aerodynamics: IEA Wind Task 47" where results on Task 47 are presented to Danish industry: The last Danish event in November 2024 was combined with a plenary project meeting [16]. At all these events, industry highlighted the importance of the work done by TURBINIA.

Additionally Italian ExCo members organize on a bi-annual basis, an Italian "IEA Wind Day", a workshop to facilitate the exchange of information among the Italian participants to IEA TCP Wind Tasks. The Italian TURBINIA participants (CNR-INM, University of Firenze, PolliBa, La Sapienza and Roma Tre), played an active role in these workshops.

Furthermore TNO presented results from IEA TCP Wind at a Dutch national knowledge event on IEA research related to the energy transition in the built environment. This knowledge event was attended by more than 100 participants. The TNO presentation was largely devoted to Task 39 (Silent Wind Turbines) and Task 41 (Distributed wind) but it highlighted the connections from these Tasks to TURBINIA because aerodynamics is also of importance for acoustics and small wind turbines, leading to a statement that "Aerodynamics is everywhere, even in the built environment").

In addition to conventional dissemination methods such as workshops, conference presentations, and journal articles, TURBINIA (similar to the previous IEA Task 29) is distinguished by the active participation of numerous MSc and PhD students. These students consistently report that their involvement is a valuable learning experience, not only in terms of content but also in developing personal skills through meeting attendance and networking with other task participants. After graduation, many of these students secure positions within the wind energy sector, where they continue to disseminate TURBINIA knowledge. This contributes significantly to the Human Capital Agenda, while the outflow of knowledgeable students to industry is an effective form of dissemination. Examples of (PhD) student reports are [17–25].

Another important aspect related to Human Capital is the fact that many academic participants conduct research in TURBINIA but they are also teaching. They often incorporate the latest insights from TURBINIA into their curricula, ensuring that students receive the most up-to-date information regarding wind turbine aerodynamics.

Chapter 2

Work plan, deliverables, meetings

2.1 Workplan

The workplan of TURBINIA has been approved at the on-line 86th Executive Committee Meeting in October 2020. TURBINIA started on January 1st 2021 and ended on December 31st 2024.

TURBINIA consisted of 2 main technical work packages (WP's):

- WP1: Measurements and simulations, this includes a cooperation on the field of specialised aerodynamic experiments see chapter 5 and the simulation of DanAero measurements, see chapter 3.
- WP2: (Turbulent) calculations on 15MW Reference Wind Turbine. This includes a mutual comparison of calculational results from low versus high fidelity models, starting with simple preparatory calculations to assure that the input descriptions are well established culminating in full turbulent calculations, see section 4

Apart from that, there was WP3 on cooperation and communication with other IEA Tasks, see Chapter 6. Finally WP0 concerned the management of the Task.

During the project, minor adjustments were made to the original planning, as detailed in the progress reports presented to the IEA Executive Committees. Specifically, the scope of Work Package 2 (IEA 15 MW RWT) was slightly reduced. The initial plan involved a preliminary case and two turbulent cases with multiple iterations, but this was considered too ambitious in view of a delayed delivery of the final 15 MW RWT model where moreover a consistent comparison of turbulent calculations on a large wind turbines turned out to be far from straightforward and needed more time than anticipated. It was therefore decided to limit the calculations to a preliminary case and 1 turbulent round round with at least 2 iterations.

2.2 Deliverables and milestones

Table 2.1 presents the planned deliverables and milestones in chronological order. As noted in Section 2.1, the scope of Work Package 2 was slightly reduced. Consequently, the original deliverables D2.4, D2.7, D2.8, D2.11, and D2.12—related to the second turbulent round on the 15 MW RWT—are no longer included.

Additionally, a new deliverable, D1.7, was introduced: a "recommendation document" addressing various practical challenges associated with aerodynamic measurements.

Most deliverables consist of reports, many of which were intended for internal use to support project progress. These include management reports as well as documents outlining calculation cases and their results. While deadlines for submitting these calculation rounds were generally met, participants were allowed to submit revised results if they had valid reasons. As a result, the timeline in Table 2.1 was kept slightly more flexible than initially planned.

The most relevant outcomes for third parties—particularly the final calculational results and their analysis—are included in the present report. The collaboration on aerodynamic measurements is

documented in D1.7, which is also available to third parties. In addition, several dissemination efforts were undertaken to share findings with external audiences, as outlined in section 1.3. External parties who would like to test their models with TURBINIA results can request input and output data of calculational rounds at TNO.

More specifically, the following comments can be given on the deliverables.

- WP1: Most of the deliverables relate to the first and second round of calculations on Danaero. D1.1, and D1.3 and D1.5 refer to the first round on DanAero. They were more or less finished in time and they led to a second round at sheared conditions which are reported in D1.2, D1.4 and D1.6. In section 3.4 it is explained that they have culminated in an extra research effort to understand the cause for an overprediction of loads from engineering models. Since this is a finding with very high impact the delivery date of D1.6 was delayed to December 1st 2024. D1.7 is a deliverable which was added to the work plan, it refers to the document in which recommendations are given on how to do aerodynamic measurements.
- WP2: The deliverables D2.1 and D2.2 relate to the preliminary calculations on the 15 MW RWT. They were delayed compared to the original schedule because the final design data of the IEA 15 MW RWT were supplied later than planned. Although a preliminary design of IEA 15 MW RWT was available already in an earlier stage the contact persons from IEA Task 37 recommended to wait with releasing the calculational rounds for Task 47 until the final design data became available. This happened in the beginning of 2022 after which preliminary calculations on the IEA 15 MW RWT were defined for axi-symmetric steady conditions. Additionally an input (e.g. a CAD file) had to be generated for the more advanced CFD codes in TURBINIA. This was done with help from NREL and DLR and it was finished in September 2022 after which the CFD calculations started. Thereafter a turbulent round on the 15 MW RWT was carried out and reported in D2.3, D2.5, D2.7 and D2.9 where a second iteration was reported in D2.10 (although as mentioned before the distinction between the first and second iteration was less strict than anticipated).
- WP0: The most important deliverable from WP0 is the present final report. Apart from this, there are several management deliverables (i.e. progress reports for IEA ExCo meetings, minutes of plenary meetings). Moreover a sharepoint has been created on a DTU server where documents and data have been uploaded. The progress reports have, in line with IEA procedures, been delivered to the IEA ExCo at least two weeks before their meetings. Written reports and a presentation were delivered at least one meeting per year. The minutes of the plenary meetings, see section 2.3 are given in [16,26–29]. Several web meetings have been organised which are reported in minutes as well [30].

The minutes have been distributed between the TURBINIA partners and they are together with the presentations, uploaded to the sharepoint. External parties who would like to test their models with TURBINIA results can request input and output data of the various calculational rounds at the OA (D0.7)

The following comments can be given on the milestones:

- The Milestones M0.1 (The potential participants will meet and inform the other participants and the Operating Agent on the chances of their definite participation. A preliminary agreement on work plan and deliverables will be reached. Task leaders are appointed where appropriate) and M0.2. (The participants will meet and reach consensus on the final version of the work plan) were passed according to plan.
- M1.2 (First round of turbulent DanAero calculations and analysis). At the progress meeting on November 28 and 29, 2022 this milestone was passed.
- M1.1 (Mid Term Assessment of experiments: In a meeting with the experimental parties the experiences until then are summarized in terms of lessons learned, problems and solutions, and recommendations for better experiments. Moreover it forms a decision point whether data from the new experiments are in a stage already that they can be used in a new simulation round). At the progress meeting on February 13 2023 this milestone was passed although confidentiality issues prevents the use of most

measurements as a basis for a new calculational round. D.1.7 is added to the deliverable list and measurements on turbines with a relatively small scale are shared which makes that it is still fair to conclude that this milestone passed.

- M2.1 and M2.2 (confidence in aerodynamic and aero-elastic reference of 15 MW RWT). At the meeting on May 22. 2023 it was, despite some uncertainties, considered fair to conclude that these milestones are passed where a further assessment of the aero-elastic modelling has been done through analysis led by PoliMi, see section 4.4.
- M1.3 (Second round of DanAero calculations and analysis). At the progress meeting on November 28 2024 this milestone was completed.
- M2.3 (15 MW RWT: First round of turbulent calculations on 15 MW turbine completed and analysed). At the progress meeting on November 28 2024 this milestone was completed.

2.3 Meetings

Within TURBINIA, a total of five hybrid plenary meetings were conducted. These took place in May 2022 at TNO Delft, November 2022 at the University of Stuttgart, May 2023 at Strathclyde Glasgow, May 2024 at the University of Firenze, and November 2024 at Danish Technical University. The meetings at TNO Delft, Strathclyde, and the University of Firenze were scheduled to precede conferences such as the Science of Making Torque Conference or the Wind Energy Science Conference. Since many TURBINIA participants were already attending these conferences, combining them with TURBINIA meetings provided an opportunity for personal gatherings with minimal financial and environmental impact.

In addition there have been on-line plenary Team meetings which roughly speaking were held at a two months interval. The results of these meetings are reported in minutes see section 2.2. Apart from these plenary meetings, there were specific meetings on particular subjects (e.g. experiments, CFD modelling, definition of cases). These meetings were attended by a smaller group of participants.

No.	WP	Deliverable/Milestone	Participant/Operating Agent	Due
D0.5	0	Report: Minutes of webmeetings and face to face meetings	OA	Continuously
D0.6	0	Web Site: Web Site	OA	Continuously
M0.1	0	Milestone: The potential participants will meet and inform the other participants and the Operating Agent on the chances of their definite participation. A preliminary agreement on work plan and deliverables will be reached. Task leaders are appointed where appropriate	All	01/04/21
D1.1	2	Report: DanAero: Description of first calculations round	OA	31/07/21
M0.2	0	Milestone: The participants will meet and reach consensus on the final version of the work plan	All	01/09/21
D0.2	0	Report: 1st progress report	OA	01/11/22
D1.3	1	Report: DanAero: Comparison between results of first round	OA	15/11/22
D1.5	1	Report: DanAero: Minutes of telcon with analysis of results of first round	OA	15/12/22
M1.2	1	Milestone: First round of turbulent DanAero calculations and analysis completed	All	15/12/22
D2.1	2	Report: 15MW RWT: Comparison between calculated and measured aerodynamic properties, preliminary calculations	OA	31/12/22
D2.2	2	Report: 15MW RWT: Comparison between calculated and measured aero-elastic properties, preliminary calculations	OA	31/12/22
M2.1	2	Milestone: Confidence in aerodynamic reference of 15 MW RWT	All	31/12/22
M2.2	2	Milestone: Confidence in aero-elastic reference of 15 MW RWT	All	31/12/22
D1.2	1	Report: DanAero: Description of second calculations round	OA	31/12/22
M1.1	1	Milestone: Mid Term Assessment of experiments: In a meeting with the experimental parties the experiences until then are summarized in terms of lessons learned, problems and solutions and recommendations for better experiments. Moreover it forms a decision point whether data from the new experiments are in a stage already that they can be used with confidence and with added value in a new simulation round	All	01/01/23
D2.3	2	Report: 15MW RWT: Description of first calculational round at turbulent conditions	OA	01/10/23
D0.3	0	Report: 2nd progress report	OA	01/11/23
D2.5	2	Report: 15MW RWT: Comparison between results of first turbulent round, first iteration	OA	30/01/24
D2.9	2	Report: 15MW RWT: Minutes of telcon with analysis of results of first round, first iteration	OA	28/02/24
D1.4	1	Report: DanAero: Comparison between results of second round	OA	01/04/24
M1.3	1	Milestone: Second round of DanAero calculations and analysis completed	All	01/05/24
D2.6	2	Report: 15MW RWT: Comparison between results of first round, second iteration	OA	15/09/24

No.	WP	Deliverable/Milestone	Participant/Operating Agent	Due
D2.10	2	Report: 15MW RWT: Minutes of telcon with analysis of results of first round, second iteration	OA	15/10/24
M2.3	2	Milestone: 15MW RWT: First round of turbulent calculations on 15 MW turbine completed and analysed	All	15/10/24
D0.4	0	Report: 3rd progress report	OA	01/11/24
D1.6	1	Report: DanAero: Minutes of telcon with analysis of results of second round	OA	01/06/24
D1.7	1	Report: Document on how to do aerodynamic measurements	OA	15/12/24
D0.7	0	Database: Web Based Validation Platform	OA/OST	15/12/24
D0.1	0	Report: Draft final report	OA	15/12/24

Table 2.1: Planned deliverables and milestones in chronological order

Chapter 3

DanAero comparison rounds

3.1 Introduction

Section 1.1 describes how, since the 1990s, measurement data from field tests and wind tunnels have been used to validate a wide range of models. This led to the conclusion that low fidelity blade-element/momentum (BEM) models, as used by the industry, provide good results under relatively simple conditions, such as uniform, constant inflow conditions and straight blades.

However, for non-uniform inflow conditions and turbulent inflow, which are prescribed for fatigue load simulations, achieving satisfactory agreement between predictions and measurements, as well as between low and high fidelity simulations, has been more challenging [31, 32]. Additionally, as explained in section 1.1, the upscaling of wind turbine rotors has made these inflow non-uniformities (e.g., shear, veer, turbulence) more significant.

Validation exercises for non-uniform and turbulent inflow are complicated by the often unknown spatial and temporal distribution of the wind field, making consistent comparison against field measurements difficult. Furthermore, inflow agreement between lifting line and CFD simulations is complicated by the different positions for specifying the wind input, namely in the rotor plane or further upstream in the domain. Although engineering methodologies have been devised to circumvent this challenge [33], it remains impossible to achieve identical inflow conditions due to the propagation and convection of the wind field within the CFD domain and its interaction with the rotor.

The objective of the activities described in this chapter is to assess model accuracy in non-uniform inflow conditions and to identify areas for improvement. Comparisons are made between simulations from various models and measurements from the DanAero experiment, where simulations are also compared mutually. This work was presented at the Science of Making Torque conference in 2024 [34].

3.2 Methodology

The DanAero turbine has been a subject of investigation, which is a 80-m rotor diameter 2.3-MW wind turbine instrumented with, among others, surface pressure measurement equipment at four sections along the blade at 13, 19, 30 and 37 m from the rotor center [35] [36]. A detailed aero-elastic model description has been released that enables aero-elastic modeling of the turbine. Integrating the measured surface pressures around the sectional airfoil contour resulted in the chord-normal and tangential pressure forces at these four stations. Meteorological measurements were performed using a mast located 313 m (3.9 diameters) in the southwesterly direction (237°) upwind from the turbine. The meteorological mast included cup and sonic anemometers at 7 heights up to 93 m. More details about instrumentation can be found in [37]. The participants are summarized in Table 3.1, contributing by using a variety of rotor aerodynamic models ranging in fidelity from BEM to blade-resolved CFD. A wind field was generated using a constrained turbulence generator [55], which was fed with time-resolved meteorological mast measurements at seven different heights. A time series of approximately 400 s was selected with relatively constant rotational speed in partial load, i.e. without pitch angle variation, featuring an average axial induction factor of around 0.4 and angle of attack of 4 degrees

Table 3.1: High-level summary of participant codes and settings.

Legend Entry	Participant	Code Name	Aero Model	Struc. Model	Ref.
DNV_Bladed_BEM	DNV	Bladed	BEM	multi-body	[38]
DNV_Bladed_FVW	DNV	Bladed	LL-FVW	multi-body	[38, 39]
DLR_TAU	DLR	Tau	RANS	rigid	[40]
DTU_EllipSys3D	DTU	EllipSys3D	RANS	multi-body	[41, 42]
DTU_HAWC2	DTU	HAWC2	BEM	multi-body	[43, 44]
DTU_HAWC2NW	DTU	HAWC2	BEM plus nearwake	multi-body	[45, 46]
DTU_HAWC2NWVC	DTU	HAWC2	NW plus vortex cylinder	multi-body	[47]
IFPEN_BEM	IFPEN	DeepLines Wind	BEM (<i>AeroDeeP</i>)	multi-body	[48]
IFPEN_VL	IFPEN	DeepLines Wind	LL-FVW (<i>CASTOR</i>)	multi-body	[48]
NREL_BEM	NREL	OpenFAST	BEM (<i>AeroDyn</i>)	modal	[49]
NREL_OLAF	NREL	OpenFAST	LL-FVW (<i>OLAF</i>)	modal	[50]
PoliMi_Cp-Lambda	PoliMi	Cp-Lambda	BEM	multi-body	[51]
TNOAero-BEM ¹	TNO	AeroModule	BEM	multi-body	[52]
TNOAero-BEM-S ¹	TNO	AeroModule	BEM (240° sector)	multi-body	[31]
TNOAero-AWSM ¹	TNO	AeroModule	LL-FVW (<i>AWSM</i>)	multi-body	[53]

¹When coupled to the structural solver Phatas [54], the legend entry is PhatAero instead of TNOAero.

Table 3.2: Summary of mean conditions and configurations for the turbulent inflow rounds.

Case Name	Hub H. Wind Speed [m/s]	Turb. Int. [%]	Rot. Speed [rpm]	Pitch [deg]	Ax. Ind. Factor [†] [-]	AOA [†] [deg]	Model Type
V1.1	6.1	7	13.2 (constant)	0.17	0.40	4	Flexible
V1.2	6.1	7	13.2 (constant)	3.00	0.25	2	Rigid
V1.3	6.1	7	13.2 (prescribed)	0.17	0.40	4	Flexible

[†] estimate at 80% span using a BEM simulation

at an 80% span. It is noted that the averaged operational and inflow conditions are identical to a previous comparison exercise in constant uniform inflow [8], which provides a foundation from which the current comparison exercise can be performed. Three different versions of this case are pursued as summarized in Table 3.2. A large number of partners then simulated the first test case with constant rotational speed and a flexible turbine model. For the lifting line codes, engineering model extensions are used to account for dynamic wake effects, yawed flow, turbulent wake state, and dynamic stall and tower stagnation, and specific details can be inferred from the references given in Table 3.1. In addition to the lifting line codes, also CFD simulations were fed with the resulting wind field. However, the initial empty box CFD simulations suffered from unrealistic coherence (apparent from the synthetic turbulence generator), which resulted in a large variety between CFD codes for the propagated wind field at the rotor disk. Therefore, it was decided to exclude CFD simulations for this round.

Before comparing the simulation results, it was ensured that identical inflow was prescribed between the different codes by monitoring the wind speed at the hub and virtual probes co-rotating with the blades. After several iterations, good results were obtained by comparing both time series as well as statistics (average and standard deviation) of hub-height and blade probe wind speeds, confirming that the simulations are aligned, and slicing through the same wind field. This is illustrated in Figure 3.1 for the time series.

Figure 3.1: Illustration of alignment between the lifting line codes by means of hub-height wind speed (top) and undisturbed wind speed as registered by a virtual blade probe at 37 m from the rotor center (below).

3.3 Results in turbulent inflow

Figure 3.2 confirms a good agreement in average load levels, visualized by the normal force from the integrated pressure distributions at the four sections. However, the standard deviation shows a large spread between measurements and models but also between the models themselves. For the measurements, the standard deviation is obtained from the integrated pressure distributions. The disagreement with measurements regarding the normal force standard deviation can originate from a large number of causes. Engineering judgement points at poor representation of the inflow as only seven points were measured at the meteorological mast. To exclude the influence of rotor speed variations, an iteration was performed with prescribed rotor speed variations based on the measurements. Figure 3.3 illustrates that this case (V1.3) does bring the simulations closer to the measurements. A closer look at the underlying cause reveals that the predicted angle of attack and lift coefficient variations (judged by standard deviation) are hardly altered from case V1.1. to V1.3. This result indicates the increase in normal force variations is caused by the apparent dynamic pressure felt by the blades, which roughly scales with the square of rotor speed times local radius. What remains is the discrepancy between the normal force standard deviation predictions from the simulations, which feature large differences up to 20% for the FVW codes.

To further investigate the cause of these differences, a new computational case was defined comparing only model results between each other. It was decided to steer away from the turbulent wake state by increasing the blade pitch angle to 3 degrees, resulting in a lower axial induction factor. In addition to that, differences in structural modeling were excluded by prescribing a rigid turbine model, arriving at the definition of case V1.2. Despite these efforts, the resulting normal force standard deviations as depicted in the bottom part of Figure 3.4 still show large differences. A closer look reveals a consistent drop from BEM to FVW type codes, in line with previous investigations [31], which indicates the differences are originating from the aerodynamic modeling. This observation is further substantiated by the differences in unsteady axial induced velocities, featuring a difference in standard deviation up to a factor close to 3. Zooming in on the underlying time series results in Figure 3.5. The frequency content can be inspected by comparing the smoothed power spectral density of the axial induced velocity, which reveals the difference in standard deviation mainly to be caused by discrepancies at 1P. However, also for the higher frequencies, more energy content can be observed for the FVW models. A deeper dive concluded that shed vorticity effects due to circulation variation in time are an important contributor to the high-frequency fluctuations observed in the FVW codes. For many of the BEM results, shed vorticity effects are also accounted for (e.g. by unsteady airfoil aerodynamic submodels [56]), but these are applied to force coefficients instead of induced velocities.

Figure 3.2: Comparison of measured and predicted normal force mean (top, standard deviation and extremes added by black and grey lines on top) and standard deviation (below) values at four radial stations 13 m, 19 m, 30 m and 37 m from the rotor center for case V1.1. The order of the bars in the plots agrees with the order of the legend entry.

Figure 3.3: Comparison of measured and predicted normal force standard deviation for case V1.3 (top, prescribed rpm time series) and comparison of predicted standard deviations of lift coefficient at 37 m from the rotor center between case V1.1 and V1.3 (bottom). The order of the bars in the plots agrees with the order of the legend entry.

Figure 3.4: Comparison of the predicted standard deviation of axial-induced velocities for case V1.2 at four radial stations 13 m, 19 m, 30 m and 37 m from the rotor center. The order of the bars in the plot agrees with the order of the legend entry.

Figure 3.5: Comparison of predicted time series (left) and smoothed power spectral density (right) of axial induced velocity at 37 m from the rotor center for case V1.3.

Table 3.3: Summary of mean conditions and configurations for the sheared inflow rounds.

Case Name	Hub H. Wind Speed [m/s]	Shear Exp [-]	Rot. Speed [rpm]	Pitch [deg]	Ax. Ind. Factor [†] [-]	AOA [†] [deg]	Model Type
V1.4	6.1	0.35	12.3	0.17	0.40	4	Rigid
V1.5	6.1	0.35	12.3	3.00	0.25	2	Rigid

[†] estimate at 80% span based on BEM simulations

Figure 3.6: Comparison of the predicted variation of axial induced velocity (left) and chordnormal force (right) with rotor azimuth angle for case V1.5 at 30 m (76%R) from the rotor center. Solid lines represent BEM-type codes, dashed lines represent the FVW codes and dotted lines represent the CFD results.

To investigate the observed differences in a more controlled manner, a code comparison round in pure vertical shear was defined, allowing CFD contributions to be included more easily.

3.4 Sheared inflow investigation

3.4.1 Methodology

The hub-height wind speed was chosen to be identical to the mean value from the turbulent round, together with blade pitch angle and rotational speed, ensuring that angles of attack remain in attached flow without dynamic stall effects. However, care has to be taken to prevent differences due to the speed-up of the flow between the ground and the rotor (altering the effective shear profile), which is taken into account for the CFD simulations but not for the BEM simulations. Therefore, the hub height of the DanAero turbine was elevated to 100 m, which was verified by FVW simulations mirrored around ground level to be a safe distance not to alter the inflow field. A shear exponent of 0.35 was prescribed, resulting in a wind speed difference of 2 m/s between the top and bottom of the rotor plane. This is roughly equivalent to a shear exponent of 0.2 in combination with the original hub height of 57 m. In addition, the tower stagnation was not modeled to focus purely on the effect of shear. Table 3.3 summarizes the two cases, denoted as V1.4 and V1.5, which differ again in the loading of the rotor as illustrated by the axial induction factor.

3.4.2 Results

A selection of representative results in terms of azimuthal variation with shear is given in Figure 3.6. Although a visual inspection of the load variation with azimuth shows the expected dip for the blade pointing down, the variation of induced velocities (and hence also of angles of attack) reveal large scatter. Previous investigations

Figure 3.7: Comparison of amplitudes of axial induced velocity (left) and normal force (right) for sheared inflow (case V1.5). The order of the bars in the plots agrees with the order of the legend entry. Please note the two CFD codes (DLR_Tau and DTU_EllipSys3D) cannot provide lifting-line-induced velocities and are therefore omitted in the plot on the left-hand side.

in vertical shear have indicated a need for a local BEM implementation to match higher-fidelity model results [57], although the resulting load amplitudes were not compared quantitatively. The compared BEM implementations all feature a local evaluation of the momentum equations, but the specific implementations seem to differ significantly, resulting in different amplitudes and phases. The normal force and induced velocity amplitudes in Figure 3.7 are comparable to previous investigations [31], now featuring results from two CFD codes and five vortex wake models. Similar to the turbulent inflow comparison, load amplitudes are up to 20% higher for standard BEM-type codes in comparison to the FVW but also CFD models.

To shed more light on the observations, the lifting line code results have been re-processed to include local axial force coefficients (using normal and tangential forces) and local axial induction factors (using axial induced velocities). As such, the level of agreement with momentum theory can be assessed. The following two main options are pursued to perform this data reduction:

- Local
The local undisturbed wind speed at the quarter chord point is used to non-dimensionalize both the axial force and induced velocities at each radial station and azimuth angle.
- Annulus
The hub-height wind speed is used to non-dimensionalize both the axial force and induced velocities, which are first averaged over all azimuth angles to determine annulus averaged values. This technique then results in a separate value for each radial position only.

In addition, the axial induction factor should be corrected for the finite number of blades, hence it should not be the local value at the blade. For the BEM simulations, this is corrected by applying the Prandtl factor; however, this is less straightforward for the vortex wake codes. The same Prandtl factor distribution with radius has been applied to post-process all BEM and FVW code results, where it is noted that this largely affects the stations at 13 m and 37 m (33%R and 92%R). Also, for the inboard stations, the contribution of drag is significant for which the inclusion in momentum theory can be debated.

The resulting plots for case V1.5 at 76% R in Figure 3.8 show that it can be inferred that, despite some outliers, most codes seem close to annular momentum theory, as the scale of variation in the plot is rather small. For the local approach, this certainly is not the case. The FVW codes (dashed lines) seem to vary with rotor azimuth at a larger angle than the BEM results, compared to the direction of the local tangent of the momentum curve. Although there is a large variety between the BEM codes (solid lines),

Figure 3.8: Comparison of agreement with the theoretical momentum curve for the annulus average (left) and local approach (right) (case V1.5 at 76%R).

Figure 3.9: Comparison of agreement with the theoretical momentum curve for the local approach with and without the dynamic inflow model (left) and for sector averaging the reference wind speed over a 240-degree-wide annular sector (right) (case V1.5 at 76%R).

Table 3.4: Summary of mean conditions and configurations for the individual pitch variation rounds.

Case Name	Hub H. Wind Speed [m/s]	Shear Exp [-]	Rot. Speed [rpm]	Pitch [deg]	Ax. Ind. Factor [†] [-]	AOA [†] [deg]	Model Type
V1.5_IPC	6.1	0.00	12.3	3.00 +/- 1.25	0.25	2	Rigid
V1.5_IPC_shear	6.1	0.35	12.3	3.00 -/+ 1.25	0.25	2	Rigid

[†] estimate at 80% span based on BEM simulations

their variation seems to align with the direction of the momentum curve, which should be the case if a standard local BEM implementation has been applied. However, the loop of several BEM results, departing from the theoretical momentum curve, is still considerable. A closer look at the cause for these differences reveals engineering models that interfere with momentum equilibrium. It was found that some models predict a non-zero dynamic inflow inertia term for this sheared case, because of assumed proportionality to the time derivative of the local rather than the annulus averaged axial-induced velocity, the effect of which is illustrated in Figure 3.9. Also, decoupling the unsteady airfoil data correction from the induction calculation was found to potentially drive the results away from momentum equilibrium. Furthermore, it was verified that the difference in load amplitude between the vortex and BEM codes is not impacted by shed vorticity effects, which are typically modeled in the BEM codes and can be considered negligible for reduced frequencies around $k=0.01$.

The fact that the local momentum plots for FVW codes feature a loop that is systematically angled differently, compared to the slope of the theoretical momentum curve, questions the applicability of local momentum theory for non-uniform inflow conditions. Considering a full 360-degree annulus is balanced by the force of a finite number of blades, the representative free-stream velocity and axial force coefficient (as used in momentum theory), could be hypothesized to be averaged over an azimuthal sector. Post-processing the force and induction results in a sector-averaged reference wind speed, shown in Figure 3.9, which improves the agreement of vortex code results with the theoretical momentum curve. Implementation of this concept in a BEM code has been pursued in the TNOAero-BEM-sector results, which predicts results closer to FVW codes as illustrated in Figures 3.6 to 3.9.

3.4.3 Non-uniformity by pitch angle variation

The observation that BEM codes struggle with performing in non-uniform inflow conditions has been coupled to the fact that the underlying one dimensional axial momentum equation assumes that the inflow conditions are axi-symmetric (or uniform) with respect to the streamtube considered. In sheared inflow conditions (or any other non-uniform inflow condition such as turbulent or waked inflow), it may be clear that this condition is violated. However, the same can be posed for the loads, which are also not uniform with respect to the streamtube considered. Another means to create this asymmetry in terms of loads in a controlled way is by applying blade pitch angle variations. To create an analogy with the sheared inflow case, a harmonic pitch angle variation was designed as a function of blade azimuth angle, resulting in a similar load amplitude as for the sheared case. As such, the harmonic pitch variation was actuated at a decrease of 1.25 degree for the blade pointing up and an increase of 1.25 deg for the blade pointing down (Case V1.5_IPC), without having a vertical shear. For Case V1.5_IPC_shear, the inverse of the mentioned pitch angle variation was implemented together with the vertical wind shear, to observed whether the two effect can be cancelled out. The two additional load case variations are summarized in Table 3.4. These two cases were then ran by a limited number of participants, making sure there is a good representation of BEM, FVW and CFD codes. The results are illustrated in Figure 3.10 and 3.11 for forces and axial induced velocities. Here it can be observed that the normal force amplitude is indeed comparable to the sheared case in Figure 3.6. However the load amplitudes seem much more in agreement between the different code types. This also holds for the axial induced velocities. As a consequence, the momentum curves are in good agreement with local and rotor averaged momentum theory in Figure 3.12. Hence it can be concluded that although non-uniformity in the inflow is problematic for most BEM type codes, this is not the case for non-uniformity in terms of loads.

Shifting the attention to a mixture of both uniformities, the pitch variation in Case V1.5_IPC_shear was designed to cancel out the load variation due to shear. Figure 3.13 confirms the load variations to decrease,

Figure 3.10: Comparison of chordnormal force for case V1.5_IPC. Variation with rotor azimuth angle at 30 m (76%R) from the rotor center (left) and amplitudes (right).

Figure 3.11: Comparison of axial induced velocities for case V1.5_IPC. Variation with rotor azimuth angle at 30 m (76%R) from the rotor center (left) and amplitudes (right).

Figure 3.12: Comparison of agreement with the theoretical momentum curve for the annulus average (left) and local approach (right) (case V1.5_IPC at 76%R).

Figure 3.13: Comparison of chordnormal force (left) and axial induced velocity (right) variation with rotor azimuth angle at 30 m (76%R) from the rotor center for case V1.5_IPC_shear.

Figure 3.14: Comparison of agreement with the theoretical momentum curve for the annulus average (left) and local approach (right) (case V1.5_IPC_shear at 76%R).

but they do not fully cancel out. The trend from the two CFD codes is distinctively different from the BEM type codes, featuring two similar peaks. Despite a level offset, the trend from the FVW code seems to agree with with CFD. The axial induced velocity variation in the bottom of Figure 3.13 shows a clear difference in amplitude again, dependent on code type and its implementation. The momentum curves in Figure 3.14 show the familiar pattern again in agreement with the conventional shear case.

It is hypothesized however, that if the pitch actuation as function of blade azimuth would be different between the blades, a dynamic wake effect will make its entry, as the wake velocities will change in time for each rotor-azimuthal sector. As a consequence, the resulting combination of non-uniform and dynamic wake effects is expected to pose a challenge for BEM type codes. This has previously been demonstrated by wind tunnel tests [58], where pitching steps were executed for one out of three blades only, showcasing a good agreement with measurements for a FVW simulation but poor for the BEM type simulation. The observations and improvements are subject to further investigation and part of the ongoing efforts within IEA Wind Task 47.

3.5 Summary of results on DanAero comparison round

An aero-elastic code comparison in turbulent inflow, focusing on the 2.3-MW DanAero field turbine, has been executed within the framework of IEA Wind Task 47, with contributions from a wide variety of aero-elastic codes. The results indicate that although average load patterns are in good agreement, this does not hold for the unsteady loads that drive fatigue damage and aero-elastic stability. A simplified comparison round in vertical shear was initiated to investigate the observed differences in a more controlled manner. A consistent offset in load amplitude was observed between CFD and FVW codes on the one hand and BEM-type codes on the other hand. To shed more light on the observations, dedicated efforts are ongoing to pinpoint the causes for these differences, leading to guidelines for an improved BEM implementation. Surprisingly, rotor plane non-uniformity in terms of force (by individual blade pitching) instead of inflow, resulted in good agreement between the different fidelity codes. The results point at improving the integration of engineering models and consideration of momentum in sectors or azimuth averaging to pave the way forward.

Chapter 4

IEA 15MW RWT comparison rounds

4.1 Introduction

After the comparison rounds that subjected the DanAero experiment, the focus shifted to the modelling challenges of large wind turbines, more representative of today's market. Several participants of TURBINIA performed simulations with a variety of aerodynamic codes (both CFD and lifting line codes) featuring the IEA15 MW reference wind turbine [59], which features a 242 m diameter rotor rated at 15MW. The results from the calculations were compared mutually.

The first comparison round has been performed for constant, axial flow and can be considered a preparatory case to ensure consistent modeling in terms of input and output. After this round the focus shifted to a case featuring turbulent inflow. Section 4.2 is dedicated to the first round comparison results in constant, axial flow. Section 4.3 describes the second round comparison results in turbulent inflow. The latter two sections describe the main results of the comparison.

4.2 Preparatory Case: Constant, axial flow

4.2.1 Methodology

Two cases are defined as summarized in Table 4.1, purposely selecting an operational point around design conditions in partial load. For one simulation the turbine is modeled flexible, for the other one tower, rotor etc. should be modeled rigid. Here one can distinguish the lifting line variables (angle of attack, induced velocities etc.) for the lifting line codes and the pressure distributions for the CFD and panel codes that resolve the blade geometry. Both code types supply the integral forces and sectional force distributions which are compared. All variables are displayed as supplied. An exception lies in the non-dimensionalized values of normal and tangential force. These are non-dimensionalized using undisturbed local dynamic pressure (determined from wind and local rotational speed) to allow for a solid comparison of airfoil coefficients between experiment and simulations along the span without the complications of uncertainty in rotor induced velocities. The definition for the normal force, which is equivalent to the tangential force can be given as

$$\text{Fnc_qc} = \frac{\text{Fn}}{0.5\rho(U_\infty^2 + (\omega r)^2)c}, \quad \text{with} \quad (4.1)$$

Fnc_qc	[-]	Non-dimensionalized chordnormal force
Fn	[N/m]	Chordnormal force
ω	[rad/s]	Rotor speed
ρ	[kg/m ³]	Air density
U_∞	[m/s]	Wind speed
r	[m]	Local radius
c	[m]	Local chord.

Another exception lies in the axial force and torque which are post-processed to thrust and power coefficients Cd_{ax} and Cp using

$$\text{Cd}_{\text{ax}} = \frac{\text{Fax}}{0.5\rho U_\infty^2 \pi R^2}, \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Cp} = \frac{\text{Torque } \omega}{0.5\rho U_\infty^3 \pi R^2}, \quad \text{with} \quad (4.2)$$

Cd_{ax}	[-]	Axial force coefficient
Cp	[-]	Power coefficient
Fax	[N]	Rotor axial force
Torque	[Nm]	Rotor torque
R	[m]	Rotor radius.

The flatwise moment Mflat is another deduced variable which has been added to this comparison round. For the simulation results, a script was used to linearly integrate the given force distribution perpendicular and tangential to the rotor plane along the blade span resulting in the flap- and leadwise moments, which are rotated using the pitch angle to obtain the flatwise moment. The legend of each graph refers to the parties and their codes that were used to perform the simulations. The participants are summarized in Table 4.2, contributing by using a variety of rotor aerodynamic models ranging in fidelity from BEM to blade-resolved CFD.

4.2.2 Lifting line variables

The lifting line codes do not resolve the blade geometry, but make use of airfoil data. As a consequence, the so-called lifting line variables can be calculated along the span of the blade, which are needed to resolve the sectional velocity triangle that results in angle of attack and lift and drag through the airfoil polar look-up table combined with the effective apparent velocity. The effective velocity U_{eff} (Figure 4.1) is in good agreement between the codes, indicating that the inputted operational conditions are consistent between the codes. Small differences can be observed in the inboard region, where induction starts to play a role over the elsewhere dominant rotational velocity. The angle of attack AOA shows larger variations, caused by the differences in axial and tangential induced velocities U_i and V_i as shown in Figure 4.2. Generally speaking

Table 4.1: IEA 15 MW comparison cases (constant, axial flow)

Case nr	Model config [‡]	Wind speed U_∞ [m/s]	Pitch angle [°]	Rot. speed ω [rpm]	Tip speed ratio λ [-]	Angle of attack α^\dagger @80%R [°]	Axial induction factor a^\dagger @80%R [-]
V2.1	Rigid	7.5	0.0	5.33	8.9	6.5	0.3
V2.2	Flexible	7.5	0.0	5.33	8.9	6.5	0.3

[‡] Tilt, cone and yaw angles are set to zero, but blade prebend is included. The tower shadow effect is disregarded.

[†] estimate

Table 4.2: High-level summary of participant codes and settings.

Legend Entry	Participant	Code Name	Aero Model	Struc. Model	Ref.
Bladed_BEM	DNV	Bladed	BEM	multi-body	[38]
Bladed_VL	DNV	Bladed	LL-FVW	multi-body	[38, 39]
DLR_SPCK_TAU	DLR	Tau	RANS	rigid	[40]
DLR_SPCK_AD	DLR	SIMPACK-AD	BEM (AeroDyn)	multi-body	[49, 60]
DTU_EllipSys3D	DTU	EllipSys3D	RANS	multi-body	[41, 42]
DTU_HAWC2	DTU	HAWC2	BEM	multi-body	[43, 44]
DTU_HAWC2NW	DTU	HAWC2	BEM plus nearwake	multi-body	[45, 46]
DTU_HAWC2NWVC	DTU	HAWC2	NW plus vortex cylinder	multi-body	[47]
IFPEN_BEM	IFPEN	DeepLines Wind	BEM (<i>AeroDeeP</i>)	multi-body	[48]
IFPEN_VL	IFPEN	DeepLines Wind	LL-FVW (<i>CASTOR</i>)	multi-body	[48]
INM_Aeolian	CNR-INM	Aeolian	BEM	multi-body	[61]
INM_FunAero	CNR-INM	FunAero	Panel code	rigid	[62]
IWES_BD_BEM	IWES	OpenFAST	BEM (AeroDyn)	multi-body	[49]
IWES_BD_OLAF	IWES	OpenFAST	LL-FVW (OLAF)	multi-body	[50]
IWES_OpenFOAM	IWES	OpenFOAM	RANS	rigid	[63]
NREL_ED_BEM	NREL	OpenFAST	BEM (AeroDyn)	modal	[49]
NREL_ED_OLAF	NREL	OpenFAST	LL-FVW (OLAF)	modal	[50]
NREL_BD_BEM	NREL	OpenFAST	BEM (AeroDyn)	multi-body	[49]
ONERA_FAST	ONERA	FAST	URANS-AL	rigid	[64]
ONERA_PUMA	ONERA	PUMA	LL-FVW	rigid	[65]
TNOAero_ED_BEM	TNO	AeroModule	BEM	modal	[52]
TNOAero_ED_AWSM	TNO	AeroModule	LL-FVW (AWSM)	modal	[53]
TNOAero-BEM-S	TNO	AeroModule	BEM (240° sector)	rigid	[31]
PhatAero-BEM	TNO	AeroModule	BEM	multi-body	[52, 54]
TNO_OpenFOAM	TNO	OpenFOAM	RANS	rigid	[63]
PoliBa_LES	Politecnico Bari	-	LES-AL	rigid	[66]
PoliMi_Cp-Lambda	PoliMi	Cp-Lambda	BEM	multi-body	[51]
Sapienza_AL	Sapienza Rome	OpenFOAM	RANS-AL	1D-FEM	[63]
Unifi_ALM	Uni di Firenze	Converge CFD	LES-AL	modal	[67]
UU_ALM	Uppsala Uni	OpenFOAM	LES-AL	modal	[68]

Figure 4.1: Comparison of effective apparent velocity (left) and angle of attack (right) for Case V2.1 (rigid).

Figure 4.2: Comparison of axial induced (left) and tangential induced velocity (right) for Case V2.1 (rigid).

there is a good agreement between the lifting line variables in the midboard part of the blade, provided there is consistency in the used airfoil data. Larger differences exist close to the blade endings, where the modeling of tip and root effects, can create divergence.

Figure 4.3 then shows the difference (δ) between Case V2.1 and V2.2, of which the only difference is the introduction of flexibility for Case V2.2. As the blades are suspended from the root, the effects of flexibility are mostly noticeable in the outboard region of the blades. A trend difference can be observed, resulting in roughly two different groups featuring a maximum 2 degree differences in angle of attack at the tip. A closer look at the structural modeling of the underlying code groups reveals the inclusion of blade torsion as a possible candidate for the differences, which will be further discussed in section 4.2.4. A closer look at the difference in angle of attack between the rigid and flexible simulations also reveals a non-negligible effect in the inboard region for the dashed and dash-dotted FVW and AL results. This difference is attributed to the displacement of the tip in the flexible situation and its influence on the axial induced velocity, which is then also noticeable in the inboard part, irrespective of whether the torsional degree of freedom is taken into account or not.

4.2.3 CFD and panel code results

Starting with a comparison of the *sectional geometries* used by the codes, Figure 4.4 shows the shapes of the four sections. Despite the fact that for the rigid case, the geometries should be identical between the

Figure 4.3: Impact of flexibility, illustrated by difference between Case V2.1 and Case V2.2 values for angle of attack (left) and axial induced velocity (right).

Figure 4.4: Comparison of sectional geometries as outputted by the codes at 29.7 m (left) and 102.8 m from the blade root (right) for Case V2.1 (rigid).

Figure 4.5: Comparison of pressure distributions at 29.7 m (left) and 102.8 m from the blade root (right) for Case V2.1 (rigid).

codes, we can observe differences, mainly for the inboard section. A small difference in the radial position and the sectional orientation, which are difficult to define in a 3D sense, are candidates to explain the observed shape differences. The steep spanwise shape variation in the root region could explain the larger variation for the 29.7 m section, where it seems also the local twist angle is different. For the outboard section at 102.8 m it is remarkable that the relative thickness for the red line is significantly higher than the rest. Concluding, it can be questioned whether the illustrated shape deviations are a result of a different blade geometry used or of post-processing differences. The fact that the blade geometry was prescribed by an IGES file, plus the availability of common mesh files, should theoretically discard the first option.

The *pressure distribution* comparison plots for the same radial stations are given in Figure 4.5. Similar to previous work within the framework of IEA Wind, the outboard section shows a better agreement than the inboard section [8]. The main reason relates to the high local angle of attack for the inboard section, resulting in separated flow which is difficult to predict, especially for the inviscid panel code. For the outboard section, a better agreement is observed as it operates in attached flow conditions. Although small differences in the suction level over the first half-chord remain, the agreement indicates consistency in the set-up of the CFD and panel code simulations.

4.2.4 Loads, performance and deformation

The resulting *loads, performance and deformations* are then compared in Figure 4.6 to 4.9. Generally speaking the force distributions are in agreement with the observations from the lifting line variables and pressure distributions, featuring a good agreement midboard with larger discrepancies at the root and tip region. This results in differences around 5% for the integral variables such as power and axial force coefficient, and flapwise blade root moment. The flapwise deformations as modeled in the flexible Case V2.2 show a good agreement between the codes, but the trend and absolute levels of the edgewise deformation are not in line between the codes as illustrated in the right hand side plot of Figure 4.8. Looking at the participants that predict a flattening instead of increasing trend towards the tip, it becomes apparent that all of these use a modal approach for the structural dynamics, which is known to discard non-linear effects depending on the implementation. For the torsion in the left hand side plot of Figure 4.9, differences of more than a degree can be observed. The fact that a tip torsion of around 3 degrees already occurs in partial load conditions, indicates that torsion can not be neglected for large wind turbine blades. The right hand side plot further illustrates this by means of the difference in chordnormal force between the rigid and flexible case. The participant results that feature a torsional degree of freedom can clearly be distinguished from the ones without, judging by the discrepancy that starts at the midboard region and grows further outboard. The effect of flexibility was demonstrated to reduce the axial force between 5% to 10% and the power coefficient up to 3%. However, without modeling the torsional degree of freedom, a slight increase in axial force and

Figure 4.6: Comparison of chordnormal (left) and chord tangential (right) force distribution for Case V2.1 (rigid).

Figure 4.7: Comparison of rotor integral performance (left) and blade root flapwise moment (right) for Case V2.1 (rigid).

torque of less than 2% was registered due to the inclusion of flexibility. Probably this is caused by the flattening of the prebend due to the wind loads, making the blades face the wind more head-on.

4.2.5 Model types comparison

Similar to the procedure that previously was followed for the DanAero comparison rounds [8], the supplied data also gives the opportunity to calculate an average result for each code type. Here the following aerodynamic code types are distinguished:

- BEM
Blade Element Momentum methods
- FVW
Lifting line free vortex wake methods
- AL
Actuator line models

Figure 4.8: Comparison of blade flapwise (left) and edgewise deformation (right) for Case V2.2 (flexible).

Figure 4.9: Comparison of blade torsion deformation (left, Case V2.2 flexible) and difference in chordnormal force distribution between rigid and flexible case (right).

- CFD
Computational fluid dynamics codes, which resolve the blade geometry instead of using sectional airfoil data. In most cases the blade boundary layer is modeled as fully turbulent.

In addition to the code types listed above there is also a panel code that joined the comparison round, but it was excluded from the averaging as only one code is judged insufficient to perform statistics with. Besides the grouping by rotor aerodynamic model, it is also possible to distinguish the structural models used to calculate the blade deformation:

- modal
Linearized model using modal reduction approach
- multibody
Non-linear model using a flexible connection between multiple bodies

A summary of the codes used to determine the averages is given in Table 4.3. The aerodynamic model

Table 4.3: Summary of codes used for code type averaging (axial flow)

Code type	Code names
BEM	Bladed_BEM, DLR_SPCK_AD, DTU_HAWC2, INM_Aeolian, IWES_BD_BEM NREL_ED_BEM, NREL_BD_BEM, TNO_ED_BEM, PhatAero-BEM, PoliMi-Cp-Lambda
FVW	Bladed_VL, IWES_BD_OLAF, NREL_ED_OLAF, ONERA_PUMA, TNO_ED_AWSM
AL	ONERA_Fast, Sapienza_AL, Unifi_ALM, UU_ALM
CFD	DLR_SPCK_TAU, DTU_EllipSys3D, IWES_OpenFOAM, TNO_OpenFOAM
modal	NREL_ED_BEM, TNO_ED_BEM
multibody	Bladed_BEM, DLR_SPCK_AD, DTU_HAWC2, INM_Aeolian, IWES_BD_BEM NREL_BD_BEM, PhatAero-BEM, PoliMi-Cp-Lambda

grouping is performed for the rigid case only, to prevent mixing up with discrepancies due to the structural model. Following this reasoning, the structural model grouping is performed for BEM type codes only.

To obtain the loading averages, first the normal and tangential force are determined at the same spanwise four positions as the instrumented sections using linear interpolation from the supplied radial distributions. A simple average \bar{x} is determined using

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i) \quad .$$

In addition to that, to give an indication of the variability between the results, a partly transparent band is plotted around the average of each code type illustrating the standard error x_{err} between the supplied results of a code type

$$x_{err} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n(n-1)}}.$$

The same procedure is applied to the integral forces and deformations.

The results are illustrated in Figure 4.10 for the aerodynamic model grouping. One can conclude that the level of the normal force generally agrees well between the different code types, except from the root region where apparently the airfoil polars are not representative for the blade resolved situation including rotational

augmentation. This observation can also be made for the tangential force. A slightly higher loading (15%) in terms of normal force is apparent for free vortex wake models throughout the blade span. The bands showing the variability between results from each code type are similar between the different types except for the inboard part where the separated flow region results in a larger spread between CFD results. Figure 4.11 then clearly illustrates the influence of the two mentioned effects on the integral rotor performance, with CFD featuring slightly lower and FVW slightly higher results compared to BEM and AL results.

Figure 4.12 then shows that although flapwise deformations are hardly affected by the structural model, linearization significantly impacts the predicted edgewise deformation trend. Unfortunately no torsion deformation results were available for the modal codes, but the large band in Figure 4.13 clearly illustrates the variability between the multi-body code predictions, which we already observed in the individual code results.

Figure 4.10: Comparison of model type grouping of chordnormal (left) and chord tangential (right) force distribution for Case V2.1 (rigid).

Figure 4.11: Comparison of model type grouping of integral rotor performance for Case V2.1 (rigid).

Figure 4.12: Comparison of model type grouping of blade flapwise (left) and edgewise deformation (right) for Case V2.2 (flexible).

Figure 4.13: Comparison of model type grouping of blade torsion deformation for Case V2.2 (flexible).

4.3 Second round: Turbulent inflow

After achieving consistency in the model set-up for the IEA15 MW reference wind turbine, illustrated by the outcome of preparatory cases, a more challenging test case was defined. A turbulent inflow round was defined featuring the IEA15 MW reference wind turbine.

4.3.1 Methodology

The time averaged conditions of this round are identical to the constant uniform inflow case. A turbulent wind field without vertical wind shear has been created, with a turbulence intensity of around 8%. As the primary focus is on the differences in aerodynamic modeling, the rotor is modeled rigid. See also Table 4.4 for a summary of the case definition. For the CFD modelers, the CAD geometry of the blades as defined in the preparatory case can be used. The airfoil data needed for the lifting line simulations is also identical to the preparatory case. A 3D-correction should be switched off. Unsteady airfoil correction such as dynamic stall modeling can be applied. A 250 s duration simulation is prescribed at a constant timestep corresponding to a rotor azimuthal step of 2 degrees or less. Synchronization of blade azimuth angle is enforced by specifying the starting azimuth angle of the simulation. For CFD codes, ground modeling with symmetry or slip condition

Table 4.4: IEA 15 MW comparison cases (turbulent inflow)

Case nr	Model config [‡]	Wind speed U_∞ [m/s]	Turb int TI [%]	Shear exp [-]	Pitch angle [°]	Rot. speed ω [rpm]	Tip speed ratio λ [-]	Angle of attack $\alpha@80\%R^\dagger$ [°]	Axial ind factor $a@80\%R^\dagger$ [-]
V2.3	Rigid	7.5	8	0.0	0.0	5.33	8.9	6.5	0.3

[‡] A rigid turbine model is used. Tilt and yaw angles are set to zero, but blade cone and prebend are included. The tower shadow effect is disregarded.

[†] estimate

1

is preferred to prevent build up of vertical shear. An overview of the participants and code settings can be obtained from Table 4.2.

The variables to be compared range from operational conditions (wind speed, pitch angle, rotational speed) to power and loads (axial force, blade root bending moments, chordnormal and tangential force) and lifting line variables (angle of attack, induced velocities, airfoil coefficients), where the latter are only supplied by lifting line codes. To monitor the spanwise variation of variables, probes are defined at four different radial location along the first blade. These are defined at 25%, 44%, 64% and 85% span, which corresponds to radial distances of 29.7, 53.1, 77.2 and 102.8 m respectively measured from the rotor center. To facilitate interpretation, plots with time traces, statistics (min, max, avg, stdev), bin azimuthal averages and power spectral densities (PSDs) are generated. Here the first 50 s are usually omitted to exclude transients due to initialization from the results.

Inflow generation

From IEA Wind Task 29, experience was gained in imposing turbulence inside the CFD domains and convecting these downstream towards the rotor and comparing the loads with Lifting Line (LL) or BEM codes that imposed the turbulence at the rotor plane. This resulted in good matching of average loads between the code types. For this specific task, a few adjustments are done to hopefully obtain even better agreement between codes. It has been chosen to use two turbulence planes; one for CFD to be imposed 300 m upstream, and then one from each CFD code extracted in an empty box simulation for the LL/BEM codes to be imposed at the rotor plane position. By doing so, we minimize the discrepancies from the previous task due the flow development between the imposed plane and the rotor. Instead, we use planes extracted at the two positions, so that the development (however without the effect from rotor induction) is largely included. An initial input plane extracted from CFD should hopefully likewise reduce the drop in turbulence intensity seen in some CFD codes when imposing the turbulence planes from the Mann-box generator. By this, the precursor simulation works as an initial filter, which ensures a better match in the turbulence seen at the rotor across the codes.

Figure 4.14: Illustration of inflow generation procedure. The left figure shows Mann input sampled for CFD runs after 200m. The right figure shows empty box simulation with CFD planes imposed 300m upstream and new planes sampled at the rotor plane.

Plane creation A turbulence box has been created using first a Mann box generator, and then filtered through a CFD simulation (precursor), in order to make the box more “CFD-friendly”. The input Mann box was created with the following inputs and scaled to TI of 12.6% (mean overall) before being inputted to the CFD Precursor run. This box was then inserted to an empty CFD domain 500 m upstream of the rotor

Table 4.5: Mann box input settings

Size	4096x1024x1024 m
Points	1024x256x256
Ae-factor	1
Gamma	3
L	90.0 m
Scale-factor	0.2

position. New planes were sampled 300 m upstream of the rotor position (so after 200 m convection from input plane) for CFD simulations. The TI of the CFD input plane (averaged in space and time) is 9.6% so a drop of 3 percent points has been seen from the Mann box to the precursor sampling.

As mentioned, for the lifting line simulations, planes from empty box CFD simulations should be used, sampled at the rotor plane position. To be able to compare the lifting line results to rotor CFD simulations, the time delay due to the different starting point 300 m upstream instead of the rotor plane for the lifting line simulations needs to be accounted for. In addition to a simple convection at the freestream wind speed of 7.5 m/s (amounting to 40 s), the additional time delay due to rotor blockage needs to be added as well. To determine the magnitude of this delay, several methods can be used such as cross correlation between empty box and rotor simulation results [33]. In reality the magnitude of this delay is subject to spatial variation across the rotor plane since the induction is distributed non-uniformly. For the current project, the approach taken is to use CFD results from a uniform inflow simulation and determine a spanwise average of the induction at the different upstream stations, see also Figure 4.15. An additional 3.4 s delay was determined by integrating this wind speed over the region between 300 m upstream and the rotorplane.

Figure 4.15: Variation of wind speed in the induction zone as predicted by CFD in comparison to the empty box simulation.

4.3.2 Inflow alignment between CFD codes

Although the convection differences are reduced by using the precursor CFD results as input, one would like to verify to what extent the resulting wind fields are in agreement between the CFD codes. Therefore so-called empty box simulations (i.e. without the rotor present) were carried out by the CFD participants. The resulting flow fields were compared in two different ways, both by comparing the averages and standard deviations of wind speeds as a function of axial coordinate across several slices or lateral output planes, as well as by analysing the temporal variation at pre-defined locations (so-called probes) in the virtual rotorplane. For the latter one can distinguish inertial probes (fixed in inertial reference frame) and co-rotating probes (fixed in virtual rotating reference frame), both at four different radial locations along the blade span.

Lateral output planes

The empty box simulations were carried out in order to compare the transport of turbulent structures in a vertical and lateral homogeneous flow and to assess differences in convection, dissipation and dispersion properties of the various CFD codes participating in this task.

Table 4.6: Comparison of some code properties

Solver	Converge CFD, FAST, EllipSys3D, TAU
Method	Finite Volume
Order	2nd, 3rd
Type	2 x incompressible, 2 x compressible
Mode	LES, URANS, IDDES, WMLES
Timestep Method	1 x fully unsteady, 3 x dual-time
Timestep	0.125° - 0.5°
Rotorblade Model	2 x Actuator Line, 2 x blade resolved
Meshtype	3 x structured, 1 x unstructured
Meshsize	19M (cc [‡]), 770 (cv), 55M (cc), 134M (cv)
Longitudinal size of computational mesh	19 – 25 diameter
Lateral size of computational mesh	10 – 12 diameter
Vertical size of computational mesh	4 – 6 diameter
Biggest cell size	0.5 – 32m
Smalles sell size	0.5 – 1.0m
Number of CPU's	100 – 2500
Wallclock [h]	110 [†] , 190, 124, 680

[‡] cc = cell-centered, cv = cell-vertex scheme.

[†] without initialization phase of 8 rotor revolutions

Four different codes (see Table 4.6) managed to carry out the turbulent inflow computations. The turbulent fluctuations were injected into the flow field using a source term formulation as described in [7] (p. 58) at $x = -300\text{m}$, i.e. 300m upstream of a fictitious rotor. As can be seen in Table 4.6 all codes use a finite volume formulation. The extensions of the discretized volume ("background mesh") and the smallest cell size are well in similar ranges. The biggest cell size and the meshsize respectively vary quite substantially taking into account that two methods use actuator line models for the discretization of the rotor and a cartesian background mesh. While the type of code (two codes use a compressible and two codes an incompressible formulation) is evenly distributed, the timestep method and meshtype are biased towards dual-time stepping scheme and structured meshes. Regarding the computation mode most codes apply an LES formulation while one code is using an URANS formulation. Please also refer to the code descriptions in the appendix.

Nine different positions in streamwise direction (see Table 4.7) were chosen for computing the mean wind speed and turbulent intensity. The quantities were averaged over the last 17 rotor revolutions on a plane size of 240 (= 2R, lateral) meters x 300 (vertical) meters with an output frequency of 90 signals per revolution. These laterally and timewise averaged values were then used to create nine vertical as well as nine longitudinal profiles (see Table 4.7) shown subsequently.

Table 4.7: Output Plane and vertical positions

Longitudinal position [m]	-240	-180	-120	0	60	120	180	240	300
Vertical position [m]	40	64	88	118.5	149	179	209	233.5	257.5

Figure 4.16 shows the vertical profiles at the nine different longitudinal positions for the empty box simulation. As can be seen the mean velocity is predicted very similarly by all codes. The agreement is especially good between 40 and 120m height. Slight deviations can be seen above 120m at some longitudinal positions. These are most likely attributed to the difference in turbulent intensity that are probably caused by small differences in the magnitude of the turbulent fluctuations. The differences in the turbulent intensities is more visible due to the percentage scale. The best agreement can be seen comparing the results from DTU and DLR. This might be due to the fact that the code setup of those two codes are very similar regarding the mesh and cell sizes and the computational mode and timestep settings. Overall the differences in turbulent intensity are a little bit greater at the first 3 - 4 output planes and become smaller along the streamwise direction.

Figure 4.16: Vertical Profiles of mean streamwise velocity and turbulent intensity at nine longitudinal positions for empty box simulation. $x = -240\text{m}$ (top left), -180m (top middle), -120m (top right), 0m (middle left), 60m (middle middle), 120m (middle right), 180m (bottom left), 240m (bottom middle), 300m (bottom right)

Figure 4.17 shows as in the previous figure the excellent agreement regarding the mean velocity. With respect to the turbulent intensity the excellent agreement between the DTU and DLR results can also be seen directly, both showing the highest values for this quantity. The predicted values by the FAST code range about 0.5% to 1.5% lower which is still a good agreement.

Figure 4.17: Longitudinal Profiles of mean streamwise velocity and turbulent intensity at nine vertical positions for empty box simulation. $z = 40\text{m}$ (top left), 64m (top middle), 88m (top right), 118.5m (middle left), 149m (middle middle), 179m (middle right), 209m (bottom left), 233.5m (bottom middle) and 257.5m (bottom right).

Probes

The good agreement of the statistics for the lateral output planes gives rises to expectations for the probe analysis. The hub height wind speed probe results displayed in Figure 4.18 confirm a good agreement of the average values, but the time traces reveal differences in the higher frequency fluctuations despite a good trend agreement. This is then also reflected in the differences in the standard deviation, which in absolute sense are less than 0.2 m/s but in relative sense are significant up to 25% . A similar conclusion can be obtained for the inertial probes as illustrated in Figure 4.19. Although not shown here, the trends can be reported to be similar for the lateral and vertical wind speed components, where the mean values are approximating zero. For the rotating probes in Figure 4.20, alignment is dominated by the blade rotation slicing through the windfield, resulting in similar high frequency fluctuations, which are most predominant for the outboard probe (r4). However, if we zoom in (top middle) we can identify differences in dynamic content, which result in the differences in standard deviation quantified in the bottom plot. The differences found are in agreement with the lateral planes comparison from the previous section, acknowledging the latter comparison did not include the results from Politecnico di Bari and inertial probe data were not supplied by DLR. To illustrate

the differences in the frequency content, Figure 4.21 displays the PSD plots.

Figure 4.18: Time traces (top), average (bottom left, min and max in grey, stdev in black) and standard deviation (bottom right) of the hub height wind velocity for the Case V2.3 empty box simulations.

CaseV2.3_Ux_Inertial_stat

CaseV2.3_Ux_Inertial_std

Figure 4.19: Time traces (top), average (middle, min and max in grey, stdev in black) and standard deviation (bottom) of axial wind velocity at selected inertial probes for the Case V2.3 empty box simulations. r1 to r4 indicate the radial position, while 0/90/180/270 indicate the azimuthal position of the probes.

Figure 4.20: Time traces (top), zoomed in time traces (top middle), average (bottom middle, min and max in grey, stdev in black) and standard deviation (bottom) of axial wind velocity at selected rotating probes for the Case V2.3 empty box simulations. r1 to r4 indicate the radial position of the probes.

Figure 4.21: PSDs of axial wind velocity of the outboard inertial probe (left, r4, blade pointing up) and rotating probe (right, r4).

Effect on rotor simulations

The empty box comparison has indicated that although the mean values are good in agreement, there are some discrepancies in the unsteady flow fields. The question is to what extent these differences impact the resulting loads. Therefore the different empty boxes are fed to the same aerodynamic code. Prior to that, the flow fields from the resulting CFD rotor simulations are compared as well.

Lateral output planes Figure 4.22 shows the vertical profiles at the nine different longitudinal positions for the rotor simulation. Unfortunately the positions of the output planes have been modified during the course of the project resulting in the fact that not all partners extracted the results at the exact same locations. Nevertheless the agreement among the three codes is very good as in the previous case. In contrast to the empty box simulation it can be seen that the mean velocity is decreasing as the flow approaches the rotor due to the induction effect. Consequently the turbulent intensity before the turbine is slightly increased (since the mean velocity is contained in the denominator in the turbulent intensity). The induction predicted by DTU and DLR is almost identical. Small deviations can be seen for the induction predicted by ONERA which is probably attributed to the different rotor model (actuator line vs. blade resolved) used in this simulation. However, the prediction of the mean velocity at the rotor and almost all following streamwise positions is predicted very similarly by all codes. Even the level of turbulent intensity is very similar for all codes, although one has to keep in mind the larger scale due to the added turbulent intensity by the rotor. However, the agreement is quite remarkable considering the differences in the overall setup of the three simulations. Only in the last output plane ($x=300\text{m}$) the differences become a little bigger. This might be attributed to the coarser mesh discretization for the TAU code at this longitudinal position (and further downstream).

Figure 4.22: Vertical Profiles of mean streamwise velocity and turbulent intensity at nine longitudinal positions for rotor simulation. $x = -240\text{m}$ (top left), -180m (top middle), -120m (top right), 0m (middle left), 60m (middle middle), 120m (middle right), 180m (bottom left), 240m (bottom middle), 300m (bottom right)

Figure 4.23 again shows the development of the mean velocity and turbulent intensity along the streamwise position at different heights. The vigilant reader will notice that the decrease of the mean velocity in the first (top left) and last (bottom right) figure is less pronounced than in the other figures. This can of course be attributed to the reduced influence of the rotor at these heights since they are below and above the rotor blade tip. Leaving aside the missing longitudinal positions in the DTU output planes, the results for the mean velocity in the lower half of the rotor are excellent. Only at $z = 118.5, 149, 233.5$ and 257.5 some small deviations of unknown cause are notable for the TAU results behind the turbine. Regarding the turbulent intensity the agreement among DTU and DLR are again excellent. The comparison with the turbulent intensity predicted by ONERA is very good considering that the turbulence level is predicted slightly lower than by the two other codes most likely also due to the usage of the actuator line model in contrast to the blade resolved model for the other two codes.

Figure 4.23: Longitudinal Profiles of mean streamwise velocity and turbulent intensity at nine vertical positions for rotor simulation. $z = 40\text{m}$ (top left), 64m (top middle), 88m (top right), 118.5m (middle left), 149m (middle middle), 179m (middle right), 209m (bottom left), 233.5m (bottom middle) and 257.5m (bottom right).

Loads To monitor to what extent the variations in the flow field affect the loads, the TNOAero-BEM code is fed with different inflow fields. The chordnormal force is investigated in Figure 4.24. Here it can be observed that, similar to the inflow velocities, there is a good agreement of the mean levels, but there is a considerable difference in the unsteady content. For example there is more than 30% difference between the highest and lowest chordnormal force standard deviation at the most outboard station r4. The agreement in trends between the standard deviation of the axial velocity as encountered by the rotating probes in Figure 4.20 and the chordnormal force in Figure 4.24 is striking. From this exercise we can conclude that care should be taken when comparing rotor CFD results between each other, as the differences in loads could well be attributed by convection differences (i.e. a different inflow field at the rotor plane) instead of differences in the rotor aerodynamic modeling. Therefore it was decided to enforce an identical empty box inflow field for the lifting line simulations, which in this case was the inflow field determined from the EllipSys3D simulation from DTU.

Figure 4.24: Time traces (top), average (middle top, min and max in grey, stdev in black), standard deviation (middle bottom), bin azimuth averages (bottom left, r4) and PSD (bottom right, r4) of the normal force for the Case V2.3 rotor simulations featuring different empty box inflow fields.

4.3.3 Rotor aerodynamic modeling

After evaluating the convection differences, the focus is on identification of differences in rotor aerodynamic modeling. Before comparing the rotor simulation results it was ensured, similar to the DanAero turbulent comparison round, that identical inflow was prescribed between the different codes by monitoring the wind speed at the hub and virtual probes co-rotating with the blades. Figure 4.25 displays the agreement of the hub height wind speed and the axial wind speed of the most outboard co-rotating probe. Where the agreement is good amongst the lifting line codes (solid and dashed lines), a difference can be observed compared to the dotted lines corresponding to the CFD codes. The differences originate from the fact that for the CFD codes the rotor induction (and for blade resolved CFD also the bound vorticity effects) cannot be separated from the undisturbed wind field plus the fact that convection is different between the different CFD codes as described in the section above. Hence the lower level of the axial wind speed for the dotted lines can mainly be attributed to the rotor blockage.

Figure 4.25: Time traces of hub height wind speed (top) and axial wind velocity at the most outboard co-rotating probe (middle and bottom zoomed-in).

After confirming the inflow prescription to be consistent between the lifting line codes, the sectional loads are studied in Figure 4.26 by means of the chordnormal force. Similar to the DanAero comparison rounds, the mean load levels are in good agreement but a consistent drop in standard deviation appears from BEM to FVW codes for all radial stations. A closer look reveals that the CFD results (including the DTU EllipSys3D results of which the empty box was used to feed the inflow for the lifting line codes) are

also featuring lower standard deviation levels, more in line with the FVW results. To shed some light on the cause for the differences between BEM and FVW codes, the axial induced velocity variations are studied in Figure 4.27. Here it can be identified that most FVW codes (dashed lines) feature a more direct response to incoming velocity variations, which is partly attributed to the shed vorticity effect (see also section 3.3 on the DanAero comparison) impacting the high frequency content, but also due to less response to the slower 1P variations which dominate the unsteady loading.

Figure 4.26: Time traces (top), average (middle top, min and max in grey, stdev in black), standard deviation (middle bottom), bin azimuth averages (bottom left, r4) and PSD (bottom right, r4) of the normal force for the Case V2.3 rotor simulations.

Figure 4.27: Time traces (top), average (middle top, min and max in grey, stdev in black), standard deviation (middle bottom), bin azimuth averages (bottom left, r4) and PSD (bottom right, r4) of the axial induced velocity for the Case V2.3 rotor simulations.

4.4 Aero-elastic benchmark

This section describes aeroelastic analyses performed on the 15 MW RWT wind turbine model, (see <https://github.com/ebranlard/IEA-15-240-RWT>). The goal of this task is to compare different wind turbine analysis codes in terms of aeroelastic behavior, including both response to steady wind conditions and turbine modal content (frequencies and damping factors). The analysis is similar to the aeroelastic benchmark that was accomplished in the context of the IEA Task-29 with the NM-80 as reference turbine.

The comparison considered aeroelastic simulations and modal analysis of the entire turbine or its sub-components in different conditions. Different tests of increasing complexity, ranging from isolated blade frequency computation to full-system dynamic simulations, have been proposed to partners in order to assess, and possibly improve, the quality of their own simulation tools. Gradually increasing the complexity of the considered scenarios has the clear advantage of allowing one to detect possible inconsistencies in the modeling of turbine sub-components. Clearly, after verifying the correctness of the turbine assembly, which comprises both the sub-components and their coupling, it is possible to finally assess the goodness of the stability analysis tools, which typically complement the simulation codes for the evaluation of the damping factors of interest and for verifying the proximity of flutter boundaries. In the case of wind turbines, the modal analysis deserves special attention. In fact, when it comes to analysing rotating turbines, the stability analysis must be compliant with the periodic nature of the system and this, typically, requires the use of more sophisticated procedures. Among all, one can mention those based on linearization and Coleman transformation [69], system identification [70] or simplified Floquet analysis [71]. Although widely accepted, the aforementioned procedures present some specific approximations and criticalities that should be always checked.

This activity was supervised by the Department of Aerospace Science and Technology of Politecnico di Milano (S. Cacciola and A. Croce).

Eleven partners (DLR, DNV, DTU, IFPEN, INM, NREL, POLIBARI, TNO, UNIFI and UNIROMA, besides the supervising institution, POLIMI) participated in at least one of the comparison rounds, submitting a significant amount of results, gathered through different simulation codes and tools.

The following list reports for all Partners the tools employed in this benchmark:

- DLR: TAU
- DNV: Bladed
- DTU: HAWC2 and HAWCStab2
- IFPEN: DeepLines Wind and AeroDeeP
- INM: FUNAERO and AEOLIAN
- NREL: OpenFAST
- POLIBARI: UTD-WF
- POLIMI: Cp-Lambda
- TNO: Phatas
- UNIFI: CALMA tool
- UNIROMA: APDL and In-house FE

This chapter is organized according to the following plan. At first, Sec. 4.4.1 deals with the description of the performed analyses, which have been used for performing all comparisons. The results of such a comparison are reported in Sec. 4.4.2. Finally, Sec. 4.4.3 finalizes the chapter by summarising the main conclusions.

4.4.1 Aeroelastic simulations and modal analyses

For this benchmark, two different rotors were considered featuring a set of blades characterized by the same aerodynamic shape but two different structural properties:

- Nominal blade: characterized by fully-populated 6×6 sectional stiffness matrices. This model is hereafter called “Full” model.
- Simplified blade: characterized by a diagonal stiffness matrix. This model is hereafter called “Simplified” model.

The following set of four different tests has been considered:

1. Computation of the natural frequencies and damping factors of a clamped, non-rotating blade, *in vacuo* and without gravity, for both “Full” and “Simplified” blade models.
2. Computation of the natural frequencies and damping factors of the isolated tower, without any aerodynamic or gravity forces. For this task, the tower base is rigidly clamped to the ground, removing consequently, any foundation flexibility. Moreover, the mass of the rotor-nacelle assembly is NOT included.
3. Derivation of the Campbell diagram of the entire turbine, only for the “Simplified” model, *in vacuo* and in air computed for different wind speed values from cut-in to cut-out. Blade pitch angles and rotor speed values are selected according to the control trim set points reported in Tab. 4.8.

Table 4.8: Conditions for Campbell diagram derivation.

Wind speed [m/s]	7.5	9.0	10.9	17.0	25.0
Omega [RPM]	5.33	6.39	7.5	7.5	7.5
Pitch angle [deg]	0.0	0.0	0.0	13.95	22.69

4. Dynamic simulation in Nominal Wind Profile (NWP) conditions: for the same set points of Tab. 4.8, simplified dynamic simulations were conducted excluding the control system by fixing the rotor speed and collective pitch angle. Moreover, the inflow is set according to a Normal Wind Profile (i.e. exponential wind shear with $\alpha = 0.2$) without tower shadow, turbulence and yaw misalignment angle). Both blade models, “Simplified” and “Full”.

With reference to the triads reported in Fig. 4.28 ([72]), at steady conditions, i.e. after a possible initial transitory, the values of the following output were provided:

- Rotor thrust MEAN value [kN]
 - Display name: HCR Fx:Mean [kN]
 - Reference frame: rotor fixed frame.
- Tower-base bending moment Mx (side-side) MEAN value [kNm]
 - Display name: TB Mx:MEAN [kNm]
 - Reference frame: tower-base fixed frame.
- Tower-base bending moments My (fore-aft) MEAN value [kNm]
 - Display name: TB My:MEAN [kNm]
 - Reference frame: tower-base fixed frame
- Blade #1 root pitchable bending moment Mx (Edgewise) MEAN value [kNm]
 - Display name: BR Mx:MEAN [kNm]
 - Reference frame: blade-root pitchable frame
- Blade #1 root pitchable bending moment My (Flapwise) MEAN value [kNm]

- Display name: BR My:MEAN [kNm]
- Reference frame: blade-root pitchable frame
- Blade #1 root pitchable bending moment My (Flapwise) 1p COSINE component [kNm]
 - Display name: BR My:1pCOS [kNm]
 - Reference frame: blade-root pitchable frame
- Blade #1 root pitchable bending moment My (Flapwise) 1p SINE component [kNm]
 - Display name: BR My:1pSIN [kNm]
 - Reference frame: blade-root pitchable frame

For the computation of the periodic terms, the null value of the rotor azimuth is set when blade #1 is aligned with the axis of the tower and is pointing UPWARD (like the Mercedes logo).

Figure 4.28: Sensor reference frames ([72])

It is clear that computing the modes of the isolated blade and tower requires simple stability analysis tools. On the other hand, the evaluation of the Campbell diagram of the entire turbine needs a suitable treatment of the periodicity.

4.4.2 Results

Modes of isolated blade

In this section, the modal content of the isolated blade has been considered. All partners have been requested to provide the modal frequencies and possibly damping factors and also encouraged to assign to all modes a “name”, which could describe the related shape. Because the analysis is performed in vacuo and without gravity, the obtained results provide information related only to the inertial and structural properties of the blade.

Figure 4.29 shows on the left the frequencies and on the right the damping factors of the simple blade model (i.e. that with diagonal sectional stiffness matrices). Additionally, Fig. 4.30 shows the same quantities but considering the full blade model (i.e. that with full 6×6 sectional stiffness matrices).

From the results displayed in Fig. 4.29 and 4.30, it is clear that the agreement among partners’ predictions is excellent when we consider the first four modes (two flap-wise and two edge-wise modes). The third flapwise

Figure 4.29: Frequencies and damping of the isolated blade (simple model, with diagonal sectional properties)

Figure 4.30: Frequencies and damping of the isolated blade (full model)

Figure 4.31: Frequencies and damping of the isolated tower

mode features an acceptable agreement. As expected, the higher the frequency, the larger the spread. The apparent discrepancy in the prediction of higher modal frequencies is not surprising as the assumptions underlying the different implementations of beam models and the different procedures to extract the eigenstructure of the system may significantly impact the estimation of the modal content. A noticeable spread in the results is experienced in the torsional mode, which could indicate different treatments of the beam torsional degrees of freedom made by the different codes. This aspect may deserve further investigations as the torsion of the blade, affecting the angle of attack of the blade sections, has a significant impact on the static performance of the rotor.

Dealing with blade structural damping factors, it is possible to assess that there is a reasonable agreement for the damping of the first two blade modes (first flap and first edge). On the contrary, the discrepancy characterizing the damping factors of the other modes is quite large, an issue that is not surprising. In fact, some codes include a damping term proportional to stiffness matrix (that naturally leads to an increase of damping with frequency), while some other tools implement a beam formulation that allows the user to assign a desired value directly to the damping of each mode.

Mode of the isolated tower

Only two partners provided the obtained modal data of the isolated tower. From the plot in Fig. 4.31, it is clear that the agreement is satisfactory if we consider the frequency and the damping of the first bending mode. Dealing with the second bending mode, the outputs match in terms of frequency but feature a large discrepancy in the values of damping, which is due to the different implementations used for modeling the beam structural damping in the two simulators, as already discussed for the case of the blade modes in Sec. 4.4.2.

Campbell diagram of the entire turbine *in vacuo* and in air

The Campbell diagram is a plot of the eigen-frequencies of a rotating system as functions of the rotor angular velocity. As a rotating-bladed system, any wind turbine can be analyzed thanks to such a diagram.

In the analysis of wind turbines, the Campbell diagram is often plotted using wind speed as the independent variable. This also has the advantage of allowing one to display the behavior of the system frequencies in the full power region (region III) where the rotor speed is constant and the collective pitch angle varies.

The modal analysis of wind turbines in operating regimes presents a special feature, which is to be suitably considered: the system models are better characterized by periodic coefficients rather than invariant ones. Periodicity may arise for example from gravity, aerodynamics, shear, skew, and tower-rotor interaction. It is important to stress that, even if we assume an ideal case without aerodynamics (*in vacuo*) and without

gravity, the interaction between a flexible tower and the rotor represents a source of periodicity, which should be considered to explain the presence of the whirling modes [73].

Since the direct application of Floquet theory to the entire turbine model, which would provide the rigorous solution for the stability of LTP systems, is too computationally expensive, especially for models with thousands of degrees of freedom, like modern multibody codes, it is preferable to employ different techniques.

Partners involved in the stability analysis have mainly used two procedures, one based on the Coleman transformation and the other on system identification.

Specifically, the procedure based on the Coleman (or multiblade) transformation follows this path. At first, the system is linearized about the steady periodic trajectory that the turbine reaches for constant inputs (wind and controls) after an initial transitory. The linearized periodic system is then converted in multiblade coordinates through the Coleman transformation, which is a simple periodic and known *a priori* transformation. It is possible to demonstrate that, if the rotor has three or more blades, such a transformation reduces dramatically the periodic content present in the multiblade-converted system matrices. Such a remaining periodicity can be then removed (by azimuth-averaging or picking a representative azimuth angle) without losing the accuracy of the model. The final dynamical model turns out to be time-invariant and can be studied through a standard LTI technique, such as the Arnoldi algorithm, that can extract the lowest modes of a system without a direct solution of the eigenvalue problem. It is interesting to notice that removing the periodicity after the application of the Coleman transformation clearly generates an error in the computation of the modal characteristics. There is no rigorous procedure that can a priori estimate the upper bounds for such errors nor is there a demonstration that the simplification does not strongly propagate to system eigenstructure. However, extensive practice and comparisons performed with systems with few degrees of freedom (DOFs) show that Coleman-based algorithms generate frequency and damping estimates of high accuracy, providing that the linearization of the system be suitably performed. More in general, azimuth-averaging to remove the remaining periodicity after the Coleman transformation works well for low-order models with limited DOFs (such as ElastoDyn in OpenFAST), but does not work well for high-order models with many DOFs (such as BeamDyn in OpenFAST). This is because the eigensolution is very sensitive to small round-off error in the system matrices for high-order models. Additional material can be found in [69, 70] and references therein.

With identification-based approaches, one typically refers to non-intrusive methods which are applied directly to input-output time series generated through dynamic simulations. A linear time periodic input/output (I/O) model can be then fitted to the recorded time histories, yielding a reduced order periodic system, which can be analyzed through the Floquet theory. Clearly, if the reduced-order model has been suitably identified, its eigenfrequencies and damping factors are excellent approximations of those of the full model. As such, the methodology results model- and system-independent and does not require linearization. The clear disadvantage of this method is that the identification process cannot easily capture all highly damped modes, typically not visible in the system free-response, and hence cannot provide the related frequencies and damping factors.

In the particular case of wind turbines, suitable input-output time histories can be obtained by perturbing the system from its periodic steady state regime through impulsive forces. The type and characteristics of the perturbation should be selected to neatly excite the mode of interest, while the output(s) to be recorded are chosen so as to see the vibrations related to those modes. As an example, a side-side impulsive force applied to the tower top can be considered to excite tower side-side and whirling in-plane modes, all likely visible in the side-side tower-root bending moment.

In the next section, the Campbell diagrams of 15 MW RWT in vacuo and in air are reported.

15 MW RWT Campbell diagram in vacuo for simplified blade model

Figure 4.32, 4.33 and 4.34 displays the Campbell diagram of the entire turbine in vacuo, using the wind speed as the independent variable. The frequencies are displayed in the upper plots of each figure, whereas the bottom plots refer to the damping factors. Clearly, for this analysis in vacuo, the wind speed, in the abscissa of the plot, does not refer to the inflow velocity, which is not included in the simulations, but to the couple rotor speed-pitch angle set according to Tab. 4.8.

Although all partners' predictions capture the general behavior of the different modes, the spread in the

results is quite visible. Our opinion is that the obtained mismatch does not indicate incoherent modeling but rather that modal analyses of rotating systems with many DoFs are not trivial, even if rotor aerodynamics are not included. Consequently, the different hypotheses used within the analyses may significantly affect the results. This aspect deserves further analyses aimed at understanding the source of these discrepancies.

Finally, in terms of damping factors, all partners predicted low values, as expected.

Figure 4.32: Campbell diagram of the wind turbine in vacuo: tower modes. Upper plots: frequencies; Bottom plots: damping. Left plots: tower side-side mode; Right plots: tower fore-aft mode.

15 MW RWT Campbell diagram in air

Figure 4.35, 4.36 and 4.37 displays the Campbell diagram of the entire turbine considering also the aerodynamics, using the wind speed as the independent variable. All plots are arranged as in Sec. 4.4.2.

Due to the complexity of the analysis, a limited number of partners provided the results. Moreover, only two partners were able to compute the modal data of at least one of the high-damped out-of-plane modes, hence, the plots in Fig. 4.36 do not allow a clear comparison. However, looking at the submitted results the following comments can be derived:

- The damping factor of the tower fore-aft mode is ten times greater than that of the tower side-side mode.
- All partners predicted a mild decrease in the frequency of the collective IP (drive train) mode as the wind increases.
- A general increase in the damping of tower and in-plane modes, as the wind increases beyond 17 m/s was predicted by all partners.

Figure 4.33: Campbell diagram of the wind turbine in vacuo: Out-of-plane modes. Upper plots: frequencies; Bottom plots: damping. Left plots: rotor backward out-of-plane mode; Center plots: rotor collective out-of-plane mode; Right plots: rotor forward out-of-plane mode. Remark: NREL's results are hidden under DNV lines.

Figure 4.34: Campbell diagram of the wind turbine in vacuo: in-plane modes. Upper plots: frequencies; Bottom plots: damping. Left plots: rotor backward in-plane mode; Center plots: rotor collective in-plane mode; Right plots: rotor forward in-plane mode.

- All partners, additionally, predicted a small drop in damping values immediately around the rated speed, visible in all plots.
- Even if the trends of the damping factors may be a bit different, the average values of the damping of the low-damped mode are of similar magnitude.

Figure 4.35: Campbell diagram of the wind turbine in air: tower modes. Upper plots: frequencies; Bottom plots: damping. Left plots: tower side-side mode; Right plots: tower fore-aft mode.

Nominal Wind Profile (NWP) simulations

Full aero-elastic models have been finally used for performing time simulation of the turbine subject to a steady NWP wind. For different wind speeds within the operative range of the machine, the partners have been requested to provide some variables of interest, according to the description reported in Sec. 4.4.1. The outputs were requested for both simplified and full blade structural models.

Dealing with the “simplified” model, the comparisons among Partners’ results are shown from Fig. 4.38 to 4.41.

On the other hand, the comparison of “full” model outputs, are displayed from Fig. 4.42 to 4.45.

The agreement is reasonable for most of the variables of interest, although the spread of the results is significant especially in the lateral degrees of freedom, e.g. tower side-side and blade root edge-wise.

The same exercise made within the IEA Task-29 had shown a more accurate matching among the different Partners’ outputs. Probably, the reason for such discrepancies is to be sought in the flexibility of the 15 MW RWT.

Figure 4.36: Campbell diagram of the wind turbine in air: Out-of-plane modes. Upper plots: frequencies; Bottom plots: damping. Left plots: rotor backward out-of-plane mode; Center plots: rotor collective out-of-plane mode; Right plots: rotor forward out-of-plane mode.

Figure 4.37: Campbell diagram of the wind turbine in air: in-plane modes. Upper plots: frequencies; Bottom plots: damping. Left plots: rotor backward in-plane mode; Center plots: rotor collective in-plane mode; Right plots: rotor forward in-plane mode.

Figure 4.38: Tower base loads of the “simplified” model. Left: side-side bending moment; right plot: fore-aft bending moment.

Figure 4.39: Mean thrust of the “simplified” model.

Figure 4.40: Blade root loads of the “simplified” model. Left: edge-wise bending moment; right plot: flap-wise bending moment.

Figure 4.41: Blade root flap-wise load at 1p of the “simplified” model. Left: amplitude; right plot: phase.

Figure 4.42: Tower base loads of the “full” model. Left: side-side bending moment; right plot: fore-aft bending moment.

Figure 4.43: Mean thrust of the “full” model.

Figure 4.44: Blade root loads of the “full” model. Left: edge-wise bending moment; right plot: flap-wise bending moment.

Figure 4.45: Blade root flap-wise load at 1p of the “full” model. Left: amplitude; right plot: phase.

4.4.3 Summary and comments on Task 3.2: Aeroelastic analyses

From the analysis conducted in Task 3.2, the following conclusions can be derived.

- The different codes and different analysis tools predict with reasonable accuracy the modal characteristics of the wind turbine and of its blade.
- In terms of blade frequency, the agreement in the predictions is extremely satisfactory if one considers the lowest frequency modes, i.e. up to the third flap-wise. This fact is of paramount importance as those blade modes are highly involved in the turbine dynamics and may affect its overall response. Computations of damping factors is more affected by the details of the beam model implementation inside the simulation codes. This fact is reflected on the higher level of spread, but absolutely acceptable, in the Partners’ results. The torsional mode, on the other hand, features a higher level of spread among the results of all partners. The reason for that is, again, to be sought in the different implementations of the torsional degrees of freedom made by the simulation tools.
- Although the modal analysis of a rotating turbine is difficult due to the intrinsic periodic nature of the system, the predictions among partners are reasonably accurate especially for the modal frequencies. With a mildly higher level of spread, also damping factors get predicted reasonably well.
- The comparison of the output in NWP dynamic simulations shows a good matching among partners’ results, with a level of spread which resulted higher than that obtained during the similar exercise conducted during the IEA Task-29 with a smaller and more rigid turbine. Most probably, the flexibility of this turbine is the responsible one for the discrepancy.

4.5 Summary of results on 15 MW RWT comparison round

A large comparison exercise has been performed featuring aerodynamic and aero-elastic simulation cases on the IEA15MW reference wind turbine in various conditions, containing results of 30 codes ranging from BEM to CFD. More than 10 different variable types ranging from lifting line variables to pressures, loads and velocities have been compared for the different conditions, resulting in many comparison plots. The result is an unique insight in the current status and accuracy of rotor aerodynamic modeling. Although there are no measurements on this turbine, mutual comparison of model results provided useful insights into the performance of aerodynamic models.

Preparatory simulations on the 15 MW RWT at constant uniform conditions generally showed reasonable agreement in the aerodynamic response between low and higher-fidelity models, provided the turbine was considered rigid. However, including flexibility effects led to more discrepancies, largely due to differences in blade torsion, which in turn impacts the aerodynamics. Even at very moderate wind speeds the torsion angle

could be in the order of 2 degrees where large differences were found in the partners results. An aero-elastic benchmark showed reasonable agreement in predicting eigenfrequencies and damping for most blade and turbine modes, except for the torsional mode.

Following the preparatory cases, simulations under turbulent conditions were performed. Several turbulent boxes were generated using high-fidelity CFD models and the results were compared mutually. Some differences appeared in the turbulent boxes, which could be expected from convection differences. At first sight the differences seemed small. However, when the boxes were fed into an aero-elastic code, the differences became significant enough to affect load response. When supplying the sampled wind speeds from the turbulent box as input to lower-fidelity models, it was interesting to find that these models showed a much higher standard deviation in loads compared to higher-fidelity models. This confirms the finding from the DanAero simulations that engineering models tend to overpredict fatigue loads, particularly for large rotors. This finding has a significant impact since BEM is the industry standard.

Chapter 5

Aerodynamic experiments

5.1 Description of Experiments

5.1.1 TNO: TIADE

The Dutch TIADE project (Turbine Improvements for Additional Energy) project is a collaboration between TNO, GE Renewable Energy, and LM Wind Power. The goal is to develop and validate innovative technologies and design methods for more efficient wind turbine rotors and wind farms. The project focuses on testing various blade add-ons, such as spoilers, serrations, vortex generators, and blade tip improvements, to enhance the performance of offshore wind turbines.

A key feature of the project is to perform a long term validation campaign on a 130-meter diameter 3.8 MW turbine with a hub height of 110 meter. The turbine is variable speed and it has active blade pitch.

The turbine is located at the test site of ECN Wind Energy Facilities (EWEF) in Wieringerwerf, the Netherlands. An overview of the test site is given in figure 5.1.

The test site and its surroundings are characterised as flat terrain, consisting of mainly agricultural areas, with single farmhouses and rows of trees. The EWEF farm is very well suited for an investigation into effects at full scale because of its state-of-the-art turbines and the comprehensive and reliable measurement infrastructure for turbine and meteorological data. The TIADE turbine is located at the most westerly spot within a row of prototypes that are positioned on a line that is roughly oriented West to East, hence resulting in a relatively large undisturbed sector which includes the prevailing southwesterly wind direction. The turbine has been instrumented in accordance with IEC measurement campaigns for power and loads. Wind speed measurements have been taken from a ground-based LiDAR located 280m in southwesterly direction, which measures at 11 different heights from 42 to 188m. Also, air pressure and temperature are measured at a nearby meteorological mast. In addition to the ground-based LiDAR, two forward-looking nacelle-based LiDARs are operational on the turbine, plus a scanning LiDAR positioned 912m in southwesterly direction to measure wake characteristics.

At 25% of the blade radius, 31 pressure taps are used to measure the pressure distribution around the blade cross-section. The pressure taps on the blade surface are connected to two Scanivalve DSA3218-PTP pressure scanners through pressure tubes. Each pressure scanner can accommodate 16 signals and typically has a 0.05% full-scale long-term accuracy. The reference pressure, measured in the turbine hub, is connected to the pressure scanners by a tube of approximately 15m length. At the measurement location, the blade geometry is defined by a 38% thick airfoil closely resembling the DU-00-W-401 airfoil. The pressure sensor layout is designed using a genetic algorithm optimisation routine [74] to represent the pressure distribution as accurately as possible throughout the operational range of the turbine. Spanwise sensor staggering is applied to avoid any turbulence created by the upstream sensors interfering with measurements of the sensors further downstream. Pressure measurements were carried for a period of more than 2 years where different configurations were measured (e.g. with and without VGs and serrations). Additional measurements have been carried out with pressure sensors based on the fiber-optical principle as described in [75]. Flow visualisation measurements with tufts were carried out too. Moreover the loads at blade root, and tower were measured together with the deformations in the blade, not only in flap and edge direction but also in

Figure 5.1: Site of TIADe experiment

torsional direction.

Results from the TIADe project have been disseminated extensively amongst others in [74,76–78,78–89].

5.1.2 Fraunhofer IWES: HighRE

Within the German project "HighRe", which aimed at analyzing aerodynamics of large offshore wind turbines at high Reynolds numbers, a huge data set of aerodynamic quantities along with inflow field measurements has been generated on an Adwen AD8-180 turbine, i.e. an off-shore prototype which is located onshore within Bremerhaven's harbor in Germany. It has a rotor diameter of 180 m, a blade length of nearly 90 m and a chord length of up to 3 m at the measuring sections where the hub height reaches 115 m. The aerodynamic measurement system consists of 72 pressure sensors in total, which were distributed at two sections at one rotor blade with 18 sensors each on the pressure side and suction side, respectively. Additionally, an aerodynamic probe with 5 sensors was installed at each of the two sections. Both the sensors on the blade surface and on the aerodynamic probe are based on fiber-optical principle in detailed described in [75]. The aerodynamic system was supplemented by extensive wind measurements, which were installed on and around the turbine. Additional turbine parameters like bending moments and accelerations in the blades, tower and on the drive train, electric power and operational parameters were also measured. These measurements were accompanied by multiple lidar measurements for wind field reconstruction.

More information can be found in [90–94]

5.1.3 Ost University: Aerosense

Within the Swiss Aerosense project, a MEMS-based smart measurement system for surface pressure and acoustic data acquisition on wind turbines has been developed which can easily be installed on a rotorblade. The measurement system comprises an array of pressure sensors and an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) that can be arbitrarily installed anywhere on the blade surface.

Some first test have been done by installing the system on a 3 bladed Aventa AV-7 wind turbine with rated power of 6 kW and a rotor diameter of 12.8 meter located in Taggenberg (ZH), Switzerland, where the pressure measurements were taken at 74% span. Several measurements have been supplied to the TURBINIA project group and they can be found on [95]. The datasets contains intermittent 10 minute long measurement sessions which have been performed between December 1, 2022 and April 1, 2023 together with wind turbine data, sensor location and sensor properties metadata which are provided as JSON files.

It is emphasized that even though the turbine on which the measurements are taken is small, the number of public detailed aerodynamic measurements including public turbine data is very limited which still gives value to the data. More information is found in [96].

5.1.4 Ecole Centrale Nantes

Ecole Centrale Nantes has performed measurements on a wind farm, consisting of six 2 MW turbines. Results are reported in [97]. The focus of this experiment was on gathering a comprehensive meteorological dataset. Thereto a meteorological mast, equipped with sonic anemometers at four different heights, was installed at the center of the farm and has collected data over three years. The dataset is further supplemented with radiometer measurements for atmospheric stability analysis. Simultaneously, supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) data were acquired to provide operational information about the wind turbines, including inter alia power production and wind direction.

For the purpose of TURBINIA a very interesting activity took place which was the scanning of the outer blade geometry so that the aerodynamic input for model validation has become available. The practical experiences which were gained with scanning the geometry are described in [98]. Eventually, the quality of the scan turned out to be good enough to retrace the airfoil family. All data of the project are publicly available through the French AERIS platform.

5.1.5 DTU pressure belt and inflow measurements

During the time of the IEA Task 47 project, DTU further developed its pressure belt and inflow measurement system and conducted three measurement campaigns on full-scale MW turbines, which will be summarized

here. The measurement system has been developed since 2018 and comprises the design and manufacturing of different prototype pressure belts. In addition, wind tunnel tests have been carried out to validate the pressure distributions measured with the pressure belt by comparing with pressure measurements using the standard technique with pressure tabs drilled into the blade section model and connecting from inside to a pressure scanner.

Further components of the measurement system are a flyboard with the data acquisition system and carrying the five hole pitot tube for inflow measurements. The flyboard is attached to the leading edge of the blade section. The measurement data are transmitted with a WI-FI system to the ground and can be monitored in real time on a computer.

First full scale measurement campaign in June 2021 on a 4.2 MW turbine

The measurement campaign was carried out on the 4.3MW SWT-DD-120 turbine at the Danish National Test Field Høvsøre, within the VIA project, which had the main objective of characterizing the aerodynamic performance of a flap system on a full-scale turbine. By measuring the pressure distribution on a blade section with a 15 channel pressure belt and the inflow angle with a five-hole pitot tube, the instantaneous lift could be derived, thus studying the lift change capability of the flap system [44]. The experimental data enabled the calibration of a detailed aeroelastic model of the flap system [99].

Second full scale measurement campaign in July 2022 with pressure belt and wake rake

The DTU measurement system was further developed to include a wake rake to measure the viscous drag of the airfoil, which is the main contribution to the total drag of the airfoil at a low angle of attack. The system was installed on one of the blades of the 4.3MW SWT-DD-120 turbine mentioned above, within the VIA project. The design of the wake rake was based on previous testing of a prototype in the Poul la Cour tunnel (PLCT). This led to the following main dimensions of the wake rake: width 0.4m, four static pressure tubes, and 56 total pressure tubes.

The wake rake was attached to the wind turbine blade by four circular carbon fiber tubes attached with transition pieces of aluminum to glass fiber pads glued to the blade surface; see Fig. 5.2. An example of the instantaneous measured pressure distribution and the measured velocity deficit behind the blade section is shown in Fig. 5.3.

Figure 5.2: Left photo: The main components of the measurement system installed on the outer part of the 60m long blade. The system comprises a 32 tap pressure belt, the flyboard with the data acquisition system and carrying the five hole pitot and finally the wake rake. A zoom is presented in the right part of the figure.

Figure 5.3: A snap-shot of the instantaneous measured pressure distribution to the left and the velocity deficit measured with the wake rake to the right.

Inflow and pressure measurements in the Down Wind Experiment at NREL in April 2024

NREL conducted in spring 2024 an experiment turning a standard GE 1.5MW upwind turbine into downwind operation by different changes in control and sensors [100]. During decades there have been unanswered research questions related to the downwind rotor concept, e.g. how strong is the thumping noise from the blade passage behind the tower and what is the level of the impulsive aerodynamics loading on the blade. The main objective of the NREL experiment was to provide full-scale experimental data to answer these research questions.

To measure the detailed instantaneous aerodynamic loading on the blades and the tower DTU installed together with NREL personnel two 32 tap pressure belts on the blades together with a 64 tap belt on the tower at the same height as the passage of the outer belt on the blade, see Fig. 5.4.

Figure 5.4: The photos show the pressure belt and inflow instrumentation of the GE 1.5MW turbine in the downwind experiment. Two 32 tap extruded pressure belts were installed on the blade (photo to the left and mid) and a 64 tap belt on the tower (mid and right photo). Additionally two flyboards with data acquisition and each with a five hole pitot tube.

A measurement campaign was conducted in the last part of April 2024. Data were acquired during quite different wind conditions and a large experimental data base was established. It can be used to validate

high-fidelity CFD simulations of the complex aerodynamics from the blade passage of the tower. An example of the measured pressure response on both the blade section and the tower is shown in Fig. 5.5

Figure 5.5: In the left graph is shown the time traces from some of the pressure taps on the outboard pressure belt. On the right graph the pressure variation on the tower.

5.1.6 WiValdi

The German WiValdi Testsite is situated in Krummendeich located about 100km northwest of Hamburg and 70km northeast of Bremerhaven. The testsite comprises two state of the art Enercon turbines (termed Opus 1 & 2) with a rated power of 4.26 MW, a small experimental turbine of 500 kW (termed ExpTurb), an IEC compliant met mast, a met mast array and a data management system for a continuous storage of the data from all the sensors. A photo of the testsite can be seen in Fig. 5.6. The first LIDAR measurements have been carried out at the end of 2020. Opus 1 and Opus 2 have started their official operational phase in October 2023. The operational phase of ExpTurb is planned for the end of 2025. Once fully equipped the testsite will contain about 2600 sensors about half of them being installed on Opus 1, about 1/4 on Opus 2 and about 1/6 on the ExpTurb. Most of the sensors are concentrated for measuring the strains, deformations and accelerations on the rotor, together with measurement of the velocity field. Measurements on other turbine components (e.g. generator, tower) are also done. For the purpose of TURBINIA the measurements of direct aerodynamic properties on the blade are most important. This will be achieved via the glove measurement technique once the full testsite is up and running permanently.

Figure 5.6: The photo shows the WiValdi testsite including the IEC metmast, Opus1, the metmast array and Opus2. The components of the windfarm are ordered in the sense of the main wind direction.

5.1.7 WINSSENT test site in complex terrain

WINSSENT, see figure 5.7 represents the test facility of the Southern German wind energy research cluster WindForS to enable wind energy research in complex terrain. It is built and operated by the WindForS member ZSW. In parallel with technology developments, the test site supports answering questions regarding the social acceptance of wind energy and aligning wind energy with nature conservation. It is located at the Stöttener Berg near Geislingen an der Steige in the Swabian Alps in Baden-Württemberg, Germany, about 1hr east of Stuttgart. It is located on a forest-free plateau near a steep slope, the so-called Albtrauf. Due to the steep slope, the turbines are exposed to inclined flow and high turbulence. WINSSENT consists of two accessible, open-source, modifiable research wind turbines, four 100m met masts equipped with several ultrasonics and a variety of measuring devices, located in the surroundings. The turbines have hub heights of 73m and a rotor diameter of 50m. Their electrical power output is 750kW each, they are variable speed and have individually driven pitch motors. The turbines are equipped with different force and moment transducers as well as fibre optics for measuring transient blade deformations. Besides the met masts, synchronized scanning lidar systems, eddy-covariance systems, ceilometer, different types of measurement drones, bird radar and bat microphones enable a broad range of measurements. The IAG, University of

Figure 5.7: WINSSENT test site (www.winsent.de) with two research turbines and four 100m met masts; contact: Andreas Rettenmeier, ZSW.

Stuttgart, as WindForS representative in Turbinia, continuously reported on the erection of the test site and its instrumentation. Wind field and turbine measurements will be carried out from 2025 for scientific use in several national and European projects. Field test data will be made available as part of IEA Task 57 JAM for one of the benchmarks. Possibly detailed aerodynamic measurements could be done in a later future.

5.2 Recommendations on experiments

The aerodynamic experiments conducted in TURBINIA involve highly advanced and specialized techniques. They provide one of the few experiences available in the wind energy community on these techniques, making it valuable to share experiences and enable participants to learn from each other on how to perform these detailed measurements. To facilitate knowledge sharing and accelerate future research, the participants who conducted these aerodynamic experiments have compiled a comprehensive recommendation document, [98]. This document offers valuable insights into successful techniques, best practices, and potential pitfalls, guiding future experimentalists and preventing unnecessary duplication of effort. Amongst others, it describes experiences with several pressure measurement techniques for rotating and standstill conditions, experiences with wake rakes, techniques for measuring boundary layer transition [101] and non-dimensionalization of loads. The document also addresses the issue that hampers the full exploitation of these measurements which is the fact that the machine data on which the experiments are done generally can only be used for validation by the research party that conducted them. They may not share the data with third parties, despite previous IEA Tasks demonstrating the benefits of joint analysis of measurements. In [98], several directions for solutions on this problem are proposed, including scanning the blade geometry to determine its outer shape and aerodynamic properties as was done by Ecole Centrale de Nantes, see section 5.1.4. The practical challenges of scanning are discussed in [98]. While obtaining aerodynamic blade data would be a significant advancement, aero-elastic input data is often required as well, for which no clear solution is currently available.

Chapter 6

Cooperation with other IEA Tasks

WP3 of TURBINIA considers the cooperation between TURBINIA and other IEA Tasks which work on different fields but which have overlap/connections to aerodynamics so that they can benefit from the knowledge created in TURBINIA and vice versa. The IEA tasks which were considered to have closest relation to aerodynamics are:

- IEA Task 30 “Comparison of Dynamic Computer Codes and Models for Offshore Wind Energy”, later IEA Task 56 “OC7”. The connection to TURBINIA lies in the fact that parts of the Task 30/56 computer codes are aerodynamically driven.
- IEA Task 31, “WakeBench”, later IEA Task 57 “JAM”. The connection to TURBINIA lies in the near wake which is considered in TURBINIA and which forms the starting point of the far wake considered in WakeBench. Moreover TURBINIA will consider the turbine response to wake inflow with respect to loads where WakeBench considers the power output at wake inflow.
- IEA Task 37 “Wind Energy Systems Engineering: Integrated R, D&D” later IEA Task 55 “REFWIND”. The connection to TURBINIA lies in the use of the IEA Task 15 MW RWT from REFWIND. TURBINIA performed a detailed aerodynamic analysis on this turbine, see chapter 4. The results of these analyses were communicated to the Task 37/55 design teams. Amongst others a CAD file of the 15 MW RWT blade has been created in TURBINIA which is available to Task37/55.
- IEA Task 39 “Quiet wind turbine technologies”. The connection to TURBINIA lies in the fact that wind turbine noise is largely determined by the aerodynamics on which TURBINIA provides knowledge.
- IEA Task 46: “Erosion”. The aerodynamic knowledge and models created in TURBINIA help to assess the aerodynamic impact of erosion.
- IEA Task 52 “Large-Scale Deployment of Wind Lidar”. Although TURBINIA primarily focuses on rotor aerodynamics, accurate knowledge of the incoming wind is crucial. This is evident from the challenges in generating reliable wind input for aerodynamic models based on mast measurements taken in the DanAero experiment (see chapter 3). Additionally, the shift in aerodynamic research at the beginning of the millennium from aerodynamic field measurements (in IEA Task 14/18) to wind tunnel measurements (in IEA Task 20 and the first three phases of IEA Task 29) highlights this issue. This shift was largely driven by the uncertainties in inflow experienced during IEA Task 14/18, where wind measurements were conducted with a limited number of met masts and low resolution, leaving the inflow at the rotor largely unknown. Nowadays, the use of modern LIDAR technology, as considered in Task 52, offers a much more accurate mapping of the inflow, potentially mitigating the uncertainties experienced in the 1990s and in the DanAero experiment.

The most efficient way of cooperation was found to be through TURBINIA members which participate in other IEA Tasks as well. For almost all of the above mentioned Tasks there were also TURBINIA members participating and these members informed the TURBINIA participants on the findings from these other Tasks during several meetings. This has led to common activities with other IEA Tasks. An example is a common acoustic benchmark with Task 39 (Quiet noise technologies). This Benchmark was carried out on the DanAero experiment on the same cases which were analyzed aerodynamically in Task 29/Task47. In this acoustic benchmark calculations from a large variety of acoustic models are compared. Since the results of acoustic predictions are partly driven by the aerodynamics this makes a cooperation between Task 39 and TURBINIA very natural. As a matter it was found that the differences in acoustic calculations are inextricably connected to aerodynamic modelling of e.g. (unsteady) effects on boundary layer and pressure distribution. In this way the insights from TURBINIA on differences between aerodynamic models helped Task 39 to understand the differences in acoustic results. The results from this Benchmark are published in [102].

The same philosophy is followed in a common Benchmark with IEA Task 30 OC6 where the measurements from the EU project Unaflo are used as validation material for codes which model floating wind turbines. In the Unaflo project, [103] aerodynamic measurements are taken in the wind tunnel from PoliMi on an underground which simulates a floating wind turbine. The measurements have been simulated by Task 30 participants but also by participants from TURBINIA. Again the aerodynamic insights from TURBINIA (in

particular on dynamic inflow effects) helped IEA Task 30 and vice versa. The results from the Benchmark have been published in [104].

Also with IEA Task 46: “Erosion” a common Benchmark was held in which aerodynamic codes simulated airfoils which were subject to erosion. Both Task 46 as well as TURBINIA participants joined this Benchmark. As a result a presentation on TURBINIA was given at a Task 46 meeting in September 2024 where moreover a common Task 46/TURBINIA mini-symposium will be held on the aerodynamic effects of erosion at the Wind Energy Science Conference in June 2025,

Chapter 7

Conclusions and recommendations

7.1 Summary of main results and conclusions

The overall objective of TURBINIA was to collaborate on the field of detailed aerodynamic measurements which were mainly carried out by partners on large scale wind turbines in open air conditions, where moreover the performance of aerodynamic models for large wind turbines is assessed. Thereto various partners have collected and analyzed measurements. New techniques, including MEMS-based pressure sensors, pressure belts, and fiber optic sensors, have been developed where also wake rakes have been utilized for the first time to capture viscous drag, which is essential for wind turbine performance and cannot be measured with pressure sensors.

The experiences gained during the instrumentation process are shared in a public 'recommendation document' to aid future experimentalists in conducting detailed aerodynamic measurements, preventing the need to reinvent the wheel.

These measurements provided important validation material for the research parties involved, although most measurements and in particular the underlying machine data could not be shared among participants. The only large-scale experiment with shareable machine data is the DanAero experiment from around 2010, which makes the machine data outdated enough to be released within the consortium.

Therefore selected DanAero measurements were compared with simulations under turbulent conditions, using various models ranging from low-fidelity BEM to high-fidelity CFD, with mid-fidelity models like Free Vortex Wake methods or panel methods in between. Discrepancies are found between calculations and measurements, particularly in terms of load variations. These are partly caused by the uncertainties from the turbulent inflow which was measured with limited resolution but also from the aerodynamic modeling itself. In order to gain insight in these discrepancies, stylistic cases with prescribed shear were defined and simulated by a wide range of models. The mutual comparison of results showed that engineering models based on BEM consistently overpredict the fatigue loads compared to higher fidelity models.

Further understanding of these important discrepancies was found from case studies in which e.g. the response at Individual Pitch Control (IPC) was simulated. The IPC case without shear, which generates a more or less similar load variation as the one from the sheared case, showed good agreement between BEM-based models and higher fidelity models. This is opposite to the observation from the shear case, which indicates an impact from the free stream wind speed variation on the modelling of the induced velocity. The dependency of load results on the precise implementation of the BEM equations is not surprising, as modeling sheared conditions and other flow non-uniformities over the rotor plane inherently violate BEM assumptions. The high sensitivity to specific BEM implementations suggests there isn't a single, universally applicable BEM model, despite literature often referring to "the BEM model."

In addition to the DanAero turbine, the IEA 15 MW RWT was used as a testbed. Although there are no measurements on this turbine, mutual comparison of model results provided useful insights into the performance of aerodynamic models. Again a very wide variety of models was applied.

Preparatory simulations on the 15 MW RWT at constant uniform conditions generally showed reasonable agreement in the aerodynamic response between low and higher-fidelity models, provided the turbine was considered rigid. However, including flexibility effects led to more discrepancies, largely due to differences in blade torsion, which in turn impacts the aerodynamics. Even at very moderate wind speeds the torsion angle could be in the order of 2 degrees where large differences were found in the partners results. An aero-elastic benchmark showed reasonable agreement in predicting eigenfrequencies and damping for most blade and turbine modes, except for the torsional mode.

Following the preparatory cases, simulations under turbulent conditions were performed. Several turbulent boxes were generated using high-fidelity CFD models and the results were compared mutually. Some differences appeared in the turbulent boxes, which could be expected from convection differences. At first sight the differences seemed small. However, when the boxes were fed into an aero-elastic code, the differences became significant enough to affect load response. When supplying the sampled wind speeds from the turbulent box as input to lower-fidelity models, it was interesting to find that these models showed a much higher standard deviation in loads compared to higher-fidelity models. This confirms the finding from the DanAero simulations that engineering models tend to overpredict fatigue loads, particularly for large rotors. This finding has a significant impact since BEM is the industry standard.

The results have been shared through various publications, presentations, and other dissemination activities. In addition to conventional dissemination methods such as workshops, conference presentations,

and journal articles, the Task is notable for the large number of MSc and PhD students who actively participated in the project. After graduating, these students often find positions in the wind energy industry, where they continued to disseminate the Task knowledge. This not only contributes significantly to the Human Capital Agenda but also serves as an effective form of dissemination through the outflow of knowledgeable students.

7.2 Recommendations and future work

In TURBINIA model deficiencies were identified and directions for solutions are given but future activities should take the solution of these deficiencies a step further eventually leading to concrete improved aerodynamic models. This requires a structured, step-by-step approach using models from different degrees of fidelity to pinpoint the precise complexities causing the deficiencies.

While comparing model results on a mutual basis is highly beneficial, validation with measurements is essential, as even the most accurate models rely on certain assumptions. This necessitates detailed aerodynamic measurements, such as pressure distributions, boundary layer transition, separation, and drag, along with comprehensive inflow mapping to minimize uncertainties in inflow modeling. The significant variations in partners' results on torsion angles, along with the substantial impact of these differences for the aerodynamic modelling of large rotors, make the measurement of torsion angles crucial as well.

These recommendations can only be implemented if restrictions on sharing turbine model data are lifted, as these restrictions hinder the joint analysis of measurements taken in TURBINIA. It is still hoped that the data from the TURBINIA experiments eventually can be released but if this is not possible, a public cooperative aerodynamic field experiment on a large-scale wind turbine, utilizing advanced measurement techniques, is urgently recommended. This experiment should involve a large consortium of research community members and ideally be conducted on an existing large-scale turbine with publicly available data. An older but still relevant platform could be declassified and used as a research turbine, or access to a turbine should be found which serves as a testbed on which custom-designed blades from the research community are placed.

Although such a public experiment will be expensive, it is justified by the importance of the issue. Collaborating with other IEA Tasks could further justify the expense, as the problem of restricted turbine model data also appears in other Tasks.

Bibliography

- [1] J.G. Schepers, A. Brand, A. Bruining, J. Graham, M. Hand, D. Infield, H. Madsen, J. Paynter, and D. Simms. Final Report of IEA Annex XIV: Field Rotor Aerodynamics. Technical report, ECN-C-97-027, 1997.
- [2] J.G. Schepers et al. Final report of IEA Annex XVIII' Enhanced Field Rotor Aerodynamics Database. ECN-C-02-016, Energy Research Centre of the Netherlands, ECN, February 2002.
- [3] S. Schreck. IEA Wind Annex XX: HAWT Aerodynamics and Models from Wind Tunnel Measurements. NREL/TP-500-43508, The National Renewable Energy Laboratory, NREL, December 2008.
- [4] Schepers, J.G.; Boorsma, K.; Cho, T.; Gomez-Iradi, S.; Schaffarczyk, P.; Jeromin, A.; Shen, W.Z.; Lutz, T.; Meister, K.; Stoevesandt, B.; Schreck, S.; Micallef, D.; Pereira, R.; Sant, T.; Madsen, H.; Sorensen, N. Final report of IEA Task 29, Mexnext (Phase 1): Analysis of MEXICO wind tunnel measurements. ECN-E-12-004, Energy Research Center of the Netherlands, February 2012.
- [5] Boorsma, K.; Schepers, J.G.; Gomez-Iradi, S.; Schaffarczyk, P.; Madsen, H.A.; Sorensen, N.N.; Shen, W.Z. voorvoegsels; Lutz, T.; Schulz, C.; Herraez, I.; Schreck, S. Final report of IEA Task 29, Mexnext (Phase 2): Analysis of MEXICO wind tunnel measurements. ECN-E-14-060, Energy Research Center of the Netherlands, December 2014.
- [6] Boorsma, K.; Schepers, J.G.; Gomez-Iradi, S.; Herraez, I.; Lutz, T.; Weihing, P.; Oggiano, L.; Pirrung, G.; Madsen, H.A.; Shen, W.Z.; Rahimi, H.; Schaffarczyk, P.;. Final report of IEA Task 29, Mexnext (Phase 3): Analysis of MEXICO wind tunnel measurements. ECN-E-18-003, Energy Research Center of the Netherlands, December 2018.
- [7] J.G. Schepers, K. Boorsma, H.Aa. Madsen, G.R. Pirrung, G. Bangga, G. Guma, T. Lutz, T. Potentier, C. Braud, E. Guilmineau, A. Croce, S. Cacciola, A.P. Schaffarczyk, B.A. Lobo, S. Ivanell, H. Asmuth, F. Bertagnolio, N.N. Sørensen, W.Z. Shen, C. Grinderslev, A.M. Forsting, F. Blondel, P. Bozonnet, R. Boisard, K. Yassin, L. Höning, Bernhard Stoevesandt, M. Imiela, L. Greco, C. Testa, F. Magionesi, G. Vijayakumar, S. Ananthan, M.A. Sprague, E. Branlard, J. Jonkman, M. Carrion, S. Parkinson, and E. Cicirello. Final report of task 29, phase iv: Detailed aerodynamics of wind turbines. Technical report, May 2021.
- [8] K. Boorsma et al. Progress in the validation of rotor aerodynamic codes using field data. *Wind Energy Science*, 8(2):211–230, 2023.
- [9] J.G. Schepers, P. van Dorp, R. Verzijlbergh, and H. Jonker. Aero-elastic loads on a 10 mw turbine exposed to extreme events selected from a year-long large-eddy simulation over the north sea. *Wind Energy Science*, 2020.
- [10] J. G. Schepers and S. J. Schreck. Aerodynamic measurements on wind turbines. *WIREs Energy and Environment*, 8(1):e320, 2018.
- [11] J.G. Schepers et al. Iea task 47: Innovative aerodynamic experiment technologies and simulations on wind turbines in turbulent inflow. In *EERA JP Wind SP4 Aerodynamics Loads and Control Falcon 30/50 Workshop*, February 14 2021.

- [12] K. Boorsma, J.G. Schepers, G.R. Pirrung, H.A. Madsen, N.N. Sørensen, C. Grinderslev, G. Bangga, M. Imiela, A. Croce, S. Cacciola, F. Blondel, E. Branlard, and J. Jonkman. Challenges in rotor aerodynamic modeling for non-uniform inflow conditions. In *The Science of Making Torque from Wind (TORQUE 2024): Aerodynamics, Aeroelasticity, and Aeroacoustics*, page 022006, Florence, Italy, 2024. IOP Publishing.
- [13] K. Boorsma, J.G. Schepers, C. Grinderslev, M. Imiela, H.A. Madsen, G.R. Pirrung, and N.N. Sørensen. Differences in modeling blade- and inflow-induced rotor aerodynamic non-uniformities. *Wind Energy Science Conference*, 2025.
- [14] E. K. Fritz, C. L. Kelley, and K. A. Brown. On optimizing the sensor spacing for pressure measurements on wind turbine airfoils. *Wind Energy Science*, 9(8):1713–1726, 2024.
- [15] B. Stoevesandt, J.G. Schepers, Yuping, P. Fuglsang, editor. *Springer Handbook of Wind Turbine Aerodynamics*. Springer-Verlag, 2020.
- [16] J.G. Schepers. Minutes of the Task 47 TURBINIA meeting held at the University of Denmark (Roskilde, Denmark) on November 28 2024, December 2024.
- [17] T. Tortum. Modelling of wind turbine loads under non-uniform inflow conditions using sector averaged reference wind speed. Master’s thesis, TNO/ENSMA Poitiers, September 2023.
- [18] M. Jorissen. Dynamic stall models applied to airfoils in deep stall. Master’s thesis, TUDelft/TNO, 2023.
- [19] N.S. Dangi. Segmented gurney flaps for enhanced wind turbine wake recovery: Design, field tests and simulations. Master’s thesis, TNO/TUDelft, 2024.
- [20] M. Bouwmeesters. Stall and vortex induced vibrations in large wind turbines. Master’s thesis, TNO/TUDelft, 2023.
- [21] A. van Dijk. Calibrating stall delay models based on detailed aerodynamic measurements using uqlab. Internship report, TUDelft/TNO, February 2025.
- [22] Claudio Bernardini. *Investigating Aeroelastic and Aeroacoustic Responses of Wind Turbines using Large Eddy Simulations*. PhD thesis, Department of Mechanics, Mathematics and Management, Politecnico di Bari, 2024.
- [23] Thomas Potentier. *Impact of large spoilers on wind turbine blades using full scale and unsteady CFD simulations*. PhD thesis, Ecole de Nantes, December 2022.
- [24] E. Fritz. *Numerical and Experimental Investigations into Swept Wind Turbine Blades*. PhD thesis, TUDelft, November 2024.
- [25] L. Pagamonci. *Development of an advanced Actuator Line Method for the aero-servo-elastic simulation of floating wind turbines*. PhD thesis, University of Firenze, 2025. Draft.
- [26] J.G. Schepers. Minutes of the Task 47 TURBINIA meeting held at TNO (Delft, Netherlands) on May 31 2022, June 2022.
- [27] J.G. Schepers. Minutes of the Task 47 TURBINIA meeting held at the University of Stuttgart (Stuttgart, Germany) on November 28/29 2022, December 2022.
- [28] J.G. Schepers. Minutes of the Task 47 TURBINIA meeting held at the University of Strathclyde (Glasgow, Scotland) on May 22 2023, June 2023.
- [29] J.G. Schepers. Minutes of the Task 47 TURBINIA meeting held at the University of Firenze (Firenze, Italy) on May 28 2024, June 2024.
- [30] J.G. Schepers. Minutes of web meetings of IEA Task 47 TURBINIA held on a 2 monthly basis s.

- [31] Koen Boorsma, Florian Wenz, Koert Lindenburg, Mansoor Aman, and Menno Kloosterman. Validation and accommodation of vortex wake codes for wind turbine design load calculations. *Wind Energy Science*, 5(2):699–719, 2020.
- [32] S. Perez-Becker, F. Papi, J. Saverin, D. Marten, A. Bianchini, and C. O. Paschereit. Is the blade element momentum theory overestimating wind turbine loads? – an aeroelastic comparison between openfast’s aerodyn and qblade’s lifting-line free vortex wake method. *Wind Energy Science*, 5(2):721–743, 2020.
- [33] F Wenz, K Boorsma, T Lutz, and E Krämer. Cross-correlation-based approach to align turbulent inflow between cfd and lower-fidelity-codes in wind turbine simulations. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, volume 1618, page 062005. IOP Publishing, 2020.
- [34] K. Boorsma, J.G. Schepers, G.R. Pirrung, H.A. Madsen, N.N. Sørensen, C. Grinderslev, G. Bangga, M. Imiela, A. Croce, S. Cacciola, F. Blondel, E. Branlard, and J. Jonkman. Challenges in rotor aerodynamic modeling for non-uniform inflow conditions. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2767(2):022006, jun 2024.
- [35] H. A. Madsen, C. Bak, U. S. Paulsen, M. Gaunaa, N. N. Sørensen, P. Fuglsang, J. Romblad, N. A. Olsen, P. Enevoldsen, J. Laursen, and L. Jensen. The dan-aero mw experiments. *48th Aiaa Aerospace Sciences Meeting Including the New Horizons Forum and Aerospace Exposition*, pages 2010–0645, 2010.
- [36] C. Bak, H.A. Madsen, U. S. Paulsen, M. Gaunaa, N.N. Sørensen, P. Fuglsang, J. Romblad, N.A. Olsen, P. Enevoldsen, J. Laursen, and L. Jensen. Dan-aero mw: Detailed aerodynamic measurements on a full scale mw wind turbine. *European Wind Energy Conference and Exhibition 2010, Ewec 2010*, 2:792–836, 2010.
- [37] C. Bak, H.Aa. Madsen, M. Gaunaa N. Troldborg, W. Skrzypinski, A. Fischer, R. Møller U. Paulsen, P. Hansen, M. Rasmussen, and P. Fuglsang. DANAERO MW: Instrumentation of the NM80 turbine and meteorology mast at Tjæreborg. Report-I-0083, DTU Wind Energy, 2013.
- [38] Galih Bangga, Marina Carrion, William Collier, and Steven Parkinson. Technical modeling challenges for large idling wind turbines. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2626(1):012026, 2023.
- [39] Galih Bangga, Steven Parkinson, and Thorsten Lutz. Utilizing high fidelity data into engineering model calculations for accurate wind turbine performance and load assessments under design load cases. *IET Renewable Power Generation*, 17(11):2909–2933, 2023.
- [40] D. Schwamborn, T. Gerhold, and R. Heinrich. The dlr tau-code: Recent applications in research and industry. In *European Conference on Computational Fluid Dynamics*, 2006.
- [41] J.A. Michelsen. Basis3d - a platform for development of multiblock pde solvers. Technical report, Risø National Laboratory, 1992.
- [42] N.N. Sørensen. *General purpose flow solver applied to flow over hills*. PhD thesis, 1995.
- [43] H. Aagaard Madsen, Christian Bak, Mads Dossing, Robert Mikkelsen, and Stig Oye. Validation and modification of the blade element momentum theory based on comparisons with actuator disc simulations. *Wind Energy*, 13(4):373–389, 2010.
- [44] H. Aagaard Madsen, Torben Juul Larsen, Georg Raimund Pirrung, Li Ang, and Frederik Zahle. Implementation of the blade element momentum model on a polar grid and its aeroelastic load impact. *Wind Energy Science*, 5(1):1–27, 2020.
- [45] Georg R. Pirrung, Helge Aagaard Madsen, Taeseong Kim, and Joachim Christian Heinz. A coupled near and far wake model for wind turbine aerodynamics. *Wind Energy*, 19(11):2053–2069, 2016.
- [46] Georg Pirrung, Vasilis Riziotis, Helge Aagaard Madsen, Morten Hansen, and Taeseong Kim. Comparison of a coupled near and far wake model with a free wake vortex code. *Wind Energy Science*, 2:15–33, 2017.

- [47] A. Li, M. Gaunaa, G. R. Pirrung, and S. G. Horcas. A computationally efficient engineering aerodynamic model for non-planar wind turbine rotors. *Wind Energy Science*, 7(1):75–104, 2022.
- [48] Le Cunff C., Heurtier J.-M., Piriou L., Berhault C., Perdrizet T., Teixeira D., Ferrer G., and Gilloteaux J.-C. Fully Coupled Floating Wind Turbine Simulator Based on Nonlinear Finite Element Method: Part I - Methodology. *Proceedings of the ASME 2013 32nd International Conference on Ocean, Offshore and Arctic Engineering*, Volume 8: Ocean Renewable Energy, 06 2013. V008T09A050.
- [49] P. J. Moriarty and A. Craig Hansen. Aerodyn theory manual. Technical report, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, December 2005. NREL/EL-500-36881.
- [50] E. Branlard, I. Brownstein, B. Strom, J. Jonkman, et al. A multipurpose lifting-line flow solver for arbitrary wind energy concepts. *Wind Energy Science*, 7(2):455–467, 2022.
- [51] O.A. Bauchau, C.L. Bottasso, and Y.G. Nikishkov. Modeling rotorcraft dynamics with finite element multibody procedures. *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, 33(10):1113 – 1137, 2001.
- [52] K. Boorsma, F. Grasso, and J.G. Holierhoek. Enhanced approach for simulation of rotor aerodynamic loads. Technical Report ECN-M-12-003, ECN, presented at EWEA Offshore 2011, Amsterdam, 29 November 2011 - 1 December 2011, 2011.
- [53] A. van Garrel. Development of a wind turbine aerodynamics simulation module. Technical Report ECN-C-03-079, ECN, 2003.
- [54] C. Lindenburg and J.G. Schepers. Phatas-IV aeroelastic modelling, release "dec-1999" and "nov-2000". Technical Report ECN-CX-00-027, ECN, 2000.
- [55] Jennifer M. Rinker. PyConTurb: An open-source constrained turbulence generator. *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.*, 1037(6):062032, June 2018.
- [56] Leishman J.G. and Beddoes T.S. "A Generalised model for unsteady airfoil behaviour and dynamic stall using the indicial method". In *42th Annual Forum of the American Helicopter Society Washington DC*, June 1998.
- [57] H. Aa. Madsen et al. Blade element momentum modeling of inflow with shear in comparison with advanced model results. *Wind Energy*, 15(1):63–81, 2012.
- [58] A. Langidis, V. Petrović, S. Mancini, K. Boorsma, J.G. Schepers, and M. Kühn. Investigation of the dynamic inflow effects due to collective and individual pitch steps on a wind tunnel setup. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2507(1):012023, may 2023.
- [59] E. Gaertner et al. Definition of the IEA 15-Megawatt Offshore Reference Wind. Technical Report NREL/TP-5000-75698, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 2020.
- [60] <https://www.3ds.com/products/simulia/simpack>.
- [61] N. Aryan, L. Greco, and C. Testa. Assessment of a fast and versatile aeroelastic platform for on/off-shore wind turbine analysis. *OSSES23 Conference Proceedings*, 2023.
- [62] L. Greco and C. Testa. Wind turbine unsteady aerodynamics and performance by a free-wake panel method. *Renewable Energy*, 164:444–459, 2021.
- [63] OpenFOAM, 2020.
- [64] FAST, flexible aerodynamic solver technology, <https://w3.onera.fr/FAST>. Onera, 2022.
- [65] M. Mudry. La théorie des nappes tourbillonnaires et ses applications à l'aérodynamique instationnaire. *PhD Thesis, Paris VI University*, 1982.

- [66] G. De Cillis, O. Semeraro, S. Leonardi, P. De Palma, and S. Cherubini. Dynamic-mode-decomposition of the wake of the nrel-5mw wind turbine impinged by a laminar inflow. *Renewable Energy*, 199:1–10, 2022.
- [67] <https://convergecf.com/>.
- [68] G. P. Navarro Diaz, A. D. Otero, H. Asmuth, J. N. Sørensen, and S. Ivanell. Actuator line model using simplified force calculation methods. *Wind Energy Science*, 8(3):363–382, 2023.
- [69] M. H. Hansen. Aeroelastic stability analysis of wind turbines using an eigenvalue approach. *Wind Energy*, 7(2):133–143, 2004.
- [70] C.L. Bottasso and S. Cacciola. Model-independent periodic stability analysis of wind turbines. *Wind Energy*, 18(5):865–887, 2015.
- [71] P. F. Skjoldan and M. H. Hansen. Implicit floquet analysis of wind turbines using tangent matrices of a non-linear aeroelastic code. *Wind Energy*, 15(2):275–287, 2012.
- [72] Guideline for the certification of wind turbines. Hamburg: Germanischer Lloyd Industrial Services GmbH, 2010.
- [73] G. Bir. Multi-blade coordinate transformation and its application to wind turbine analysis. In *Proceedings of the AIAA Wind Energy Symposium*, Reno, Nevada, 1 2008.
- [74] E. Fritz, C. Kelley, and K. A. Brown. On optimizing the sensor spacing for pressure measurements on wind turbine airfoils. *Wind Energy Science*, 9(8):1713–1726, 2024.
- [75] F. M. Heckmeier et al. Development of unsteady multi-hole pressure probes based on fiber-optic pressure sensors. *Engineering Research Express*, 1(2):025023, 2019.
- [76] K. Boorsma et al. TIADe final report. Technical Report TNO 2024 R12112, TNO, 2024.
- [77] J. Peeringa et al. Field experiments of wind turbine vibrations in standstill conditions. In *EERA DeepWind Conference 2025*, 2025.
- [78] E.K. Fritz et al. Blade surface pressure measurements in the field and their usage for aerodynamic model validation. *Wind Energy*, 27(12):1483–1498, 2024.
- [79] K. Boorsma, K. Hermans, and A. Herrig. Demonstration of advanced blade measurement techniques. In *Wind Energy Science Conference 2023*, May 2023.
- [80] H. van der Mijle Meijer. Leading edge damage detection coating system for remote camera inspection. In *4th International Symposium on Leading Edge Erosion of Wind Turbine Blades*, Feb 2023.
- [81] J. Peeringa et al. Field experiments of wind turbine vibrations in stand still conditions. In *EERA DeepWind Conference 2025*, Jan 2025.
- [82] N. S. Dangi et al. Segmented gurney flaps for enhanced wind turbine wake recovery. In *Wind Energy Science Conference 2023*, May 2023.
- [83] K. Boorsma, N. S. Dangi, and E. T. G. Bot. Boosting wind farm efficiency: Application of blade turbulators. In *WindEurope 2024*, Mar 2024.
- [84] Erik Fritz, Koen Boorsma, and Andreas Herrig. Design of an Aeroelastically Tailored Wind Turbine Blade Tip for Field Experiments. Technical Report TNO 2025 R10229, TNO.
- [85] M. Turrini et al. Online application of a linear aero-hydro-elastic model for virtual monitoring of an operational wind turbine. In *WindEurope 2023*, page PO.226, Apr 2023.
- [86] Y. Liu. Enabling fast estimation for wind turbine power curves: a physics-based online learning algorithm. In *Wind Energy Science Conference 2023*, Nantes, France, June 2025.

- [87] M. Turrini et al. Advancements in wind turbine wake modelling using 3d scanning lidar measurements from a test turbine campaign. In *Wake Conference 2025*, June 2025.
- [88] K. Hermans. Challenges in measuring torsion of large rotor blades. In *EERA DeepWind Conference 2022*, Jan 2022.
- [89] M. Caboni et al. Validation of les inflow for predicting wind turbine loads in field conditions. In *Wind Energy Science Conference 2023*, May 2023.
- [90] A. Giyanani, M. Sjöholm, G. H. Thorsen, J. Schuhmacher, and J. Gottschall. Wind speed reconstruction from three synchronized short-range windscanner lidars in a large wind turbine inflow field campaign and the associated uncertainties. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2265:022032, 2022.
- [91] M. Fredebohm, J. N. Theron, L. Höning, S. Weis, B. Stoevesandt, A. Wegner, N. Denecke, H. Rosemann, and M. L. Huhn. Development of an aerodynamic measurement system for wind turbines. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2507:012020, 2023.
- [92] A. Wegner, S. Mechler, L. Höning, N. Denecke, and B. Stoevesandt. Aerodynamic conditions measured at a rotor blade of large wind turbine prototype. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2767:022024, 2024.
- [93] P. J. Meyer and J. Gottschall. Evaluation of the "fan scan" based on three combined nacelle lidars for advanced wind field characterisation. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2265:022107, 2022.
- [94] L. Höning, P. J. Meyer, M. L. Huhn, J. N. Theron, P. Thomas, A. Wegner, S. Mechler, J. Gottschall, and B. Stoevesandt. Validating low- and high-fidelity simulations of a yawed 8 mw wind turbine against measurements. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2767:022038, 2024.
- [95] Aerosense. Accessed: 2025-04-17.
- [96] Y. Marykovskiy, J. Deparday, I. Abdallah, and S. Barber. Aerosense measurements: Aventa av-7 taggenberg winter 2022-2023 campaign (version 1.0, 1-). <https://doi.org/10.34808/ypae-8684>, 2023. Dataset.
- [97] C. Braud, P. Keravec, I. Neunaber, S. Aubrun, J.-L. Attie, P. Durand, P. Ricaud, J.-F. Georgis, E. Leclerc, L. Mourre, and C. Taymans. Three-year database of atmospheric measurements combined with associated operating parameters from a wind farm of 2mw turbines and rotor geometry. *Wind Energy. Sci. Discuss.*, 2025. preprint, in review.
- [98] J.G. Schepers, K. Boorsma, J. Deparday, C. Kelley, C. Braud, A.P. Schaffarczyk, A. Gomez Gonzalez, H.A. Madsen, and S. Barber. Recommendations for performing aerodynamic field measurements on wind turbine rotors. February 25 2025.
- [99] Andrea Gamberini, Thanasis Barlas, Alejandro Gomez Gonzalez, and Helge Aagaard Madsen. Validation of aeroelastic dynamic model of active trailing edge flap system tested on a 4.3 mw wind turbine. *Wind Energy Science*, 9(5):1229–1249, 2024.
- [100] Pietro Bortolotti. Flipping the Script on Traditional Wind Turbine Technologies, 2024.
- [101] T.C.L. Fava, B.A. Lobo, A.P. Schaffarczyk, M. Breuer, D.S. Henningson, and A. Hanifi. Numerical investigation of transition on a wind turbine blade under free stream turbulence at $Re_c = 10^6$. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 1009:A52, 2025.
- [102] Franck Bertagnolio, Andreas Fischer, Christina Appel, Michaela Herr, Ferdinand Seel, Thorsten Lutz, Koen Boorsma, Gerard Schepers, Miguel Restrepo Botero, Damiano Casalino, Wouter van der Velden, Carlo R. Sucameli, and Pietro Bortolotti. Wind turbine noise code benchmark: A comparison and verification exercise. In *10th International Conference on Wind Turbine Noise*, Dublin, Ireland, June 2023.

- [103] S. Mancini, K. Boorsma, M. Caboni, M. Cormier, T. Lutz, P. Schito, and A. Zasso. Characterization of the unsteady aerodynamic response of a floating offshore wind turbine to surge motion. *Wind Energy Sci.*, 5, 1713–1730, 2020, 2020.
- [104] R. Bergua, A. Robertson, J. Jonkman, E. Branlard, A. Fontanella, M. Belloli, P. Schito, A. Zasso, G. Persico, A. Sanvito, E. Amet, C. Brun, G. Campaña Alonso, R. Martín-San-Román, R. Cai, J. Cai, Q. Qian, W. Maoshi, A. Beardsell, G. Pirrung, N. Ramos-García, W. Shi, J. Fu, R. Corniglion, A. Lovera, J. Galván, T. A. Nygaard, C. R. dos Santos, P. Gilbert, P.-A. Joulin, F. Blondel, E. Frickel, P. Chen, Z. Hu, R. Boisard, K. Yilmazlar, A. Croce, V. Harnois, L. Zhang, Y. Li, A. Aristondo, I. Mendikoa Alonso, S. Mancini, K. Boorsma, F. Savenije, D. Marten, R. Soto-Valle, C. W. Schulz, S. Netzband, A. Bianchini, F. Papi, S. Cioni, P. Trubat, D. Alarcon, C. Molins, M. Cormier, K. Brüker, T. Lutz, Q. Xiao, Z. Deng, F. Haudin, and A. Goveas. Oc-6 project phase iii: Validation of the aerodynamic loading on a wind turbine rotor undergoing large motion caused by a floating support structure. *Wind Energy Science*, 8(4):465–485, 2023.